

LEAPS-INNOV WP9 -
Innovation by Co-creation
towards Global Challenges

**CO-CREATION
CATALOGUE
OF
NETWORKS**

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CO-CREATION CATALOGUE

PREFACE

The LEAPS-INNOV project, funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 Programme (GA no.101004728), focusses on the implementation of new strategies and activities for long-term partnerships between industry and the European light sources, synchrotrons and free-electron lasers, with their tens of thousands of users.

LEAPS-INNOV aims at kick-starting the implementation of the LEAPS Technology Roadmap and, at the same time, at fostering a partnership with European industry through open innovation. It will offer joint technological developments and advanced research capabilities with LEAPS members for industry as collaborator, supplier and user.

The Co-creation catalogue (inventory) is one of the project outputs aiming to showcase the current and potential future collaboration partners in the user community. The Catalogue aims in first places to list candidates for strategic partners for LEAPS co-creation. It will also be used as a catalogue of best practice in cooperation with LEAPS facilities. Besides, it is thought to serve as an initial showcase for co-creation.

CONTENT AND STRUCTURE

The Catalogue is envisioned as a live document that will continuously be enriched with additional information provided by project partners and the user community.

As the areas of science tackled by researchers using facilities belonging to the LEAPS-INNOV consortium are very broad and interconnected, it was decided to initially choose to structure the information provided into three overarching areas linked to European Commission Missions and Clusters and to UN's SDG's. The areas are Health, Energy and Environment.

For each area, a transversal overview of the work performed at the different facilities in relation to the topic is outlined. In order to organise the input in a comprehensive way, the information is structured in lists of beamlines that provide tools and techniques applied in the area-related research, publications showcasing results of collaborations between the user community and the facilities, collaborative projects involving the facilities and the user community and user groups working with science questions related to the topic.

The information shown is obtained through workshops gathering facility representatives working with techniques used to address the three overarching areas and workshops where consortium partners meet representatives of the user community engaged in networks active on national and international level, often participating in European Partnerships and involved in projects funded by the European Framework Programme.

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(to be added)

ABBREVIATIONS

1. HEALTH

A) TOOLS / BEAMLINES

Beamline	Technique	Link
ALBA-CELLS		
BL01-MIRAS	Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy and microscopy	BEAMLINE INFORMATION — MIRAS (albasynchrotron.es)
BL09-MISTRAL	Full-field Transmission X-ray Microscopy for cryo nano-tomography in the water window for biological applications	BEAMLINE INFORMATION — MISTRAL (albasynchrotron.es)
BL06-XAIRA (end 2023)	Macromolecular Crystallography (MX) Microfocus beamline	BEAMLINE INFORMATION — XAIRA (albasynchrotron.es)
BL13-XALOC	MX beamline	BEAMLINE INFORMATION — XALOC (albasynchrotron.es)
BL31-FAXTOR (end 2024)	Fast X-ray Tomography & Radiography	BEAMLINE INFORMATION — FAXTOR (albasynchrotron.es)
Cyro-EM (end 2022)	Glacios 200kV (FEG, automated sample exchanger, Falcon 4 direct electron detector).	n.a.
DESY		
P05	Micro- and nanotomography	Beamline P05 - The Imaging Beamline at PETRA III (desy.de)
P06	Hard X-ray micro/nano-probe beamline for X-ray fluorescence (XRF), absorption spectroscopy (XAS) and diffraction (XRD); coherent diffraction/ptychography	Beamline P06 - Hard X-ray Micro/Nano-Probe (desy.de)
P11	X-ray macromolecular crystallography and bio-imaging	Beamline P11 - High-throughput Macromolecular Crystallography beamline (desy.de)
P12/EMBL	Small Angle X-ray Scattering (SAXS)	Beamline P12 - Small Angle X-Ray Scattering – EMBL
P13/EMBL	X-ray macromolecular crystallography (+ fluorescence)	Beamline P13 – Macromolecular Crystallography (embl.org)
P14/EMBL	X-ray macromolecular crystallography (+ fluorescence); T-REXX	Beamline P14 – Macromolecular Crystallography (embl.org)
ELETTRA		
IUVS	Inelastic scattering with ultraviolet radiation (UV Brillouin and UV Resonant Raman scattering)	Elettra Sincrotrone Trieste IUVS

MCX	Non-single crystal XRD, including grazing angle and reflectivity	Elettra Sincrotrone Trieste MCX
SAXS	SAXS-WAXS, GISAXS and pump-probe ps X-ray scattering	Elettra Sincrotrone Trieste SAXS
SISSI	FTIR spectro-microscopy, nano-FTIR	Elettra Sincrotrone Trieste SISSI
SYRMEP	Synchrotron Radiation for Medical Physics: Tomography, phase contrast imaging	Elettra Sincrotrone Trieste SYRMEP
TwinMic	Multifunctional - STXM, XRM, XAS, ptychography & XRF imaging	Elettra Sincrotrone Trieste TwinMic
XAFS	Hard X-ray XAFS-EXAFS in TFY and transmission	Elettra Sincrotrone Trieste XAFS
X-ray Fluorescence	XRF, XANES and TXRF in the mild X-ray energy range	Elettra Sincrotrone Trieste X-ray Fluorescence
XRD1	X-ray diffraction on cryogenic (single crystal, small and macromolecules) and not cryogenic (powders in capillaries) samples	Elettra Sincrotrone Trieste XRD1
XRD2	X-ray diffraction dedicated to high throughput macromolecular crystallography (MX) experiments	Elettra Sincrotrone Trieste XRD2
Structural Biology Lab	Protein crystallography	Elettra Sincrotrone Trieste Structural Biology Lab
NanoInnovation Lab	AFM and Fluorescence Microscopy; Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy	Elettra Sincrotrone Trieste NanoInnovationLAB
TeraFERMI	THz spectroscopy	Elettra Sincrotrone Trieste TeraFERMI
ESRF		
ID23 (1&2)	X-ray macromolecular crystallography	ID23-1: Gemini - Macromolecular Crystallography (esrf.fr) ID23-2: Gemini - Macromolecular Crystallography (esrf.fr)
ID30 (A1, B, A3)	X-ray macromolecular crystallography	ID30A-1 / MASSIF-1 (esrf.fr) ID30A-3 / MASSIF-3 (esrf.fr) ID30B / MAD (esrf.fr)
ID29	Serial crystallography	ID29 SMX - Serial Macromolecular Crystallography (esrf.fr)
BioSAXS	Small Angle X-ray Scattering (SAXS)	BM29 BioSAXS (esrf.fr)
CM01	cryoEM	CM01 Cryo-electron microscope (esrf.fr)
ID16A	X-ray nanotomography	ID16A - Nano-imaging Beamline (esrf.fr)
ID16B	Hard X-ray nanoanalysis (X-ray fluorescence and phase contrast imaging)	ID16B - Nano-analysis Beamline (esrf.fr)

ID21	Scanning X-ray microscopy	ID21 - X-ray Microscopy Beamline (esrf.fr)
BM05	Hierarchical phase-contrast Tomography	Instrumentation Facility BM05 (esrf.fr)
EuXFEL		
SPB/SFX	X-ray macromolecular crystallography (SFX)	Scientific Instrument SPB/SFX (xfel.eu)
	Scattering and diffraction (SAXS, WAXS fluctuation) Single particle imaging MHz Microscopy	
FXE	X-ray macromolecular crystallography (SFX) Spectroscopy	Scientific Instrument FXE (xfel.eu)
XBI	Laboratories for onsite sample preparation and characterisation	Biology lab (XBI) (xfel.eu)
FELIX		
IRIS	Infrared Ion Spectroscopy: Integration of mass spectrometry and IR spectroscopy, tunable IR laser radiation combined with various MS platforms (ion trap MS, FTICR-MS)	FELIX in more detail - FELIX Laboratory (ru.nl)
MAXIV		
BioMAX	X-ray macromolecular crystallography	BioMAX – MAX IV (lu.se)
MicroMAX (2023)	Rotational/serial crystallography	MicroMAX – MAX IV (lu.se)
FragMAX	Crystallographic fragment screening at BioMAX and MicroMAX	FragMAX – BioMAX Fragment Screening platform – MAX IV (lu.se)
CoSAXS	Small Angle X-ray Scattering (SAXS)	CoSAXS – MAX IV (lu.se)
SOLARIS		
SOLCRYS	X-ray macromolecular crystallography	SOLCRYS - SOLARIS National Synchrotron Radiation Centre (uj.edu.pl)
CryoEM	Cryo Electron Microscopy Facility (Titan Krios and Glacios)	Cryo-EM - SOLARIS National Synchrotron Radiation Centre (uj.edu.pl)
CIRI	Infrared imaging (FT-IR microscopy and imaging, nanoscale (s-SNOM/AFM-IR) and O-PTIR imaging)	CIRI - SOLARIS National Synchrotron Radiation Centre (uj.edu.pl)
POLYX	Policapillary X-ray Tomography	POLYX - SOLARIS National Synchrotron Radiation Centre (uj.edu.pl)
PIRX	X-ray absorption spectroscopy (XAS), (including bioXAS)	PIRX - SOLARIS National Synchrotron Radiation Centre (uj.edu.pl)
SOLEIL		

PROXIMA-1	Structural study of biological macromolecules using crystallography	PROXIMA-1 French national synchrotron facility (synchrotron-soleil.fr)
PROXIMA-2A	Microfocus beamline dedicated to biological crystallography and innovative micro-beam methodologies	PROXIMA-2A French national synchrotron facility (synchrotron-soleil.fr)
SWING	Small and Wide angle X-ray scattering, for studying complex structure samples: macromolecules, nanomaterials, soft matter, tissues	SWING French national synchrotron facility (synchrotron-soleil.fr)
ANATOMIX	Advanced Nanotomography and Imaging with coherent X rays (5-50 keV), fullfield radiography and tomography in absorption and phase contrast, with pixel sizes from 20 nm to 20 μ m	ANATOMIX French national synchrotron facility (synchrotron-soleil.fr)
NANOSCOPIUM	Hard X-ray (5-20 keV) nanoprobe beamline is dedicated to multi-technique X-ray imaging using fast scanning and high spatial resolution	NANOSCOPIUM French national synchrotron facility (synchrotron-soleil.fr)
DISCO	Dichroism, Imaging, Spectroscopy for Chemistry and biOlogy. VUV (1-10 eV) beamline with conservation of the natural polarization of the synchrotron light.	DISCO French national synchrotron facility (synchrotron-soleil.fr)
LUCIA	Line for Ultimate Characterisation by Imaging and Absorption is a "tender" (0.8-8 keV) X-ray microprobe with capabilities for chemical speciation by x-ray absorption spectroscopy (μ -XAS) and for elemental mapping by x-ray micro-fluorescence (μ -XRF)	LUCIA French national synchrotron facility (synchrotron-soleil.fr)
SMIS	Infrared spectromicroscopy beamline with capabilities in a variety of conditions including pressure, temperature, gas environment and light polarization control	SMIS French national synchrotron facility (synchrotron-soleil.fr)

B) PUBLICATIONS

Publication	Link
ALBA	
Molecular and in vivo studies of a glutamate-class prolyl-endopeptidase for coeliac disease therapy	https://www.nature.com/articles/s41467-022-32215-1
A Conformation Selective Mode of Inhibiting SRC Improves Drug Efficacy and Tolerability	https://aacrjournals.org/cancerres/article/81/21/5438/670511/A-Conformation-Selective-Mode-of-Inhibiting-SRC
Heme-binding enables allosteric modulation in an ancient TIM-barrel glycosidase	https://www.nature.com/articles/s41467-020-20630-1
Structure-based analyses of Salmonella RcsB variants unravel new features of the Rcs regulon	https://academic.oup.com/nar/article/49/4/2357/6130842
Binding site profiles and N-terminal minor groove interactions of the master quorum-sensing regulator LuxR enable flexible control of gene activation and repression	https://academic.oup.com/nar/article/49/6/3274/6163099
Structural basis of denuded glycan recognition by SPOR domains in bacterial cell division	https://www.nature.com/articles/s41467-019-13354-4
Design principles of a minimal auxin response system	https://www.nature.com/articles/s41477-020-0662-y
Live cells- synchrotron- based FTIR evaluation of metabolic compounds in brain Glioblastoma cells lines after riluzole treatment	https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/acs.analchem.1c02076
N-doped carbon dots-based cisplatin delivery system in adenocarcinoma cells: Spectroscopical and computational approach	https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0021979722007858?via%3Dihub
Study of the intracellular nanoparticle-based radiosensitization mechanisms in F98 glioma cells treated with charged particle therapy through synchrotron-based infrared microspectroscopy	https://pubs.rsc.org/en/content/articlelanding/2020/AN/C9AN02350J
Structural Changes In Cells Imaged by Soft X-ray Cryo-Tomography During Hepatitis C Virus Infection	https://pubs.acs.org/doi/full/10.1021/acsnano.6b01374
Monitoring reversion of hepatitis C virus-induced cellular alterations by direct-acting antivirals using cryo soft X-ray tomography and infrared microscopy	https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/34726165/
Unambiguous Intracellular Localization and Quantification of a Potent Iridium Anticancer Compound by Correlative 3D Cryo X-Ray Imaging	https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/full/10.1002/anie.201911510

Cells Undergo Major Changes in the Quantity of Cytoplasmic Organelles after Uptake of Gold Nanoparticles with Biologically Relevant Surface Coatings	https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/acsnano.9b09264
Two polymorphic cholesterol monohydrate crystal structures form in macrophage culture models of atherosclerosis	https://www.pnas.org/doi/10.1073/pnas.1803119115
Mode of action of quinoline antimalarial drugs in red blood cells infected by Plasmodium falciparum revealed in vivo	https://www.pnas.org/doi/10.1073/pnas.1910123116
The Capillary Morphogenesis Gene 2 Triggers the Intracellular Hallmarks of Collagen VI-Related Muscular Dystrophy	https://www.mdpi.com/1422-0067/23/14/7651
DESY	
Hybrid Biopolymer and Lipid Nanoparticles with Improved Transfection Efficacy for mRNA	https://www.mdpi.com/2073-4409/9/9/2034
Polysarcosine-Functionalized Lipid Nanoparticles for Therapeutic mRNA Delivery	https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/acsanm.0c01834
Investigation of pH-Responsiveness inside Lipid Nanoparticles for Parenteral mRNA Application Using Small-Angle X-ray Scattering	https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/acs.langmuir.0c02446
Antiviral activity of natural phenolic compounds in complex at an allosteric site of SARS-CoV-2 papain-like protease	https://www.nature.com/articles/s42003-022-03737-7
Hydrazones and Thiosemicarbazones Targeting Protein-Protein-Interactions of SARS-CoV-2 Papain-like Protease	https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fchem.2022.832431/full
X-ray screening identifies active site and allosteric inhibitors of SARS-CoV-2 main protease	https://www.science.org/doi/10.1126/science.abf7945
Structural insights into the inhibition of glycine reuptake	https://www.nature.com/articles/s41586-021-03274-z
Multimodal X-ray imaging of nanocontainer-treated macrophages and calcium distribution in the perilacunar bone matrix	https://www.nature.com/articles/s41598-020-58318-7
Observation of a single protein by ultrafast X-ray diffraction	https://www.biorxiv.org/content/10.1101/2022.03.09.483477v1
Diffraction data from aerosolized Coliphage PR772 virus particles imaged with the Linac Coherent Light Source	https://www.nature.com/articles/s41597-020-00745-2
3D virtual pathohistology of lung tissue from Covid-19 patients based on phase contrast X-ray tomography	https://elifesciences.org/articles/60408
3D virtual histopathology of cardiac tissue from Covid-19 patients based on phase-contrast X-ray tomography	https://elifesciences.org/articles/71359

A SARS-CoV-2 neutralizing antibody selected from COVID-19 patients binds to the ACE2-RBD interface and is tolerant to most known RBD mutations	https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/34273271/
Investigation of pH-responsiveness inside lipid nanoparticles for parenteral mRNA application using small-angle X-ray scattering	https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/acs.langmuir.0c02446
MyD88 TIR domain higher-order assembly interactions revealed by microcrystal electron diffraction and serial femtosecond crystallography	https://www.nature.com/articles/s41467-021-22590-6
NAD(H)-mediated tetramerization controls the activity of Legionella pneumophila phospholipase PlA _B	https://www.pnas.org/doi/10.1073/pnas.2017046118
Crystal and solution structure of NDRG1, a membrane-binding protein linked to myelination and tumour suppression	https://febs.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/full/10.1111/febs.15660
Fragment Binding to Kinase Hinge: If Charge Distribution and Local pKa Shifts Mislead Popular Bioisosterism Concepts	https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/full/10.1002/anie.202011295
Exploration of changes in spatial chondrocyte organisation in human osteoarthritic cartilage by means of 3D imaging	https://www.nature.com/articles/s41598-021-89582-w
Synchrotron XRF Analysis Identifies Cerium Accumulation Colocalized with Pharyngeal Deformities in CeO ₂ NP-Exposed <i>Caenorhabditis elegans</i>	https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/acs.est.1c08509
An NAD(+) Phosphorylase Toxin Triggers Mycobacterium tuberculosis Cell Death	https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1097276519300486
ELETTRA	
Magnesium and calcium overaccumulate in the leaves of a schengen3 mutant of <i>Brassica rapa</i> (Katarina Vogel-Mikuš et al)	https://academic.oup.com/plphys/article/186/3/1616/6217901
Hard and soft X-ray imaging to resolve human ovarian cortical structures (Lorella Pascolo et al)	http://scripts.iucr.org/cgi-bin/paper?S1600577519003680
Comparison of propagation-based CT using synchrotron radiation and conventional cone-beam CT for breast imaging (Christian Dullin et al)	https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s00330-019-06567-0
Fast, non-iterative algorithm for quantitative integration of X-ray differential phase-contrast images (Alessandro Olivo et al)	https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/33379512/
SAXS Reveals the Stabilization Effects of Modified Sugars on Model Proteins (Maria Grazia Ortore et al)	https://www.mdpi.com/2075-1729/12/1/123

Bioinspired Antimicrobial Coatings from Peptide-Functionalized Liquid Crystalline Nanostructures (Stefan Salentinig et al)	https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/acsabm.1c00415
Magnetic Levitation of Personalized Nanoparticle–Protein Corona as an Effective Tool for Cancer Detection (Caracciolo et al)	https://www.mdpi.com/2079-4991/12/9/1397
Structural Insights on Fusion Mechanisms of Small Extracellular Vesicles with Model Plasma Membranes (Mario Gimona et al)	https://pubs.rsc.org/en/content/articlelanding/2021/nr/d0nr09075a
Iron-Mediated Interaction of Alpha Synuclein with Raft-like model membranes (Valeria Rondella et al)	https://www.mdpi.com/1422-0067/20/11/2733
Cubic and Hexagonal Mesophases for Protein Encapsulation: Structural Effects of Insulin Confinement (Elisabetta Giorgini et al)	https://pubs.acs.org/doi/full/10.1021/acs.langmuir.1c01587
Pioneer settlement of the cold-water coral <i>Desmophyllum dianthus</i> (Esper, 1794) on plastic (Ilaria Corsi et al)	https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s00338-021-02131-9
High-resolution crystal structure of LpqH, an immunomodulatory surface lipoprotein of <i>Mycobacterium tuberculosis</i> reveals a distinct fold and a conserved cleft on its surface (Dr. Udupi A. Ramagopal et al)	https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0141813022009102
ESRF	
Structural insights into collagen binding by platelet receptor glycoprotein VI	https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/35245360/
Novel non-covalent LSD1 inhibitors endowed with anticancer effects in leukemia and solid tumor cellular models	https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0223523422003129#!
Investigation of Janus kinase (JAK) inhibitors for lung delivery and the importance of aldehyde oxidase metabolism.	https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/acs.jmedchem.1c01765
Structural basis of synergistic neutralization of Crimean-Congo hemorrhagic fever virus by human antibodies	https://www.science.org/doi/10.1126/science.abl6502
Structural basis of DNA methylation-dependent site selectivity of the Epstein–Barr virus lytic switch protein ZEBRA/Zta/BZLF1	https://academic.oup.com/nar/article/50/1/490/6459095
Epitope length variants balance protective immune responses and viral escape in HIV-1 infection.	https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2211124722001760
An engineered protein-based submicromolar competitive inhibitor of the <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> virulence factor aureolysin	https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2001037022000022
A non-catalytic herpesviral protein reconfigures ERK-RSK signaling by targeting kinase docking systems in the host.	https://www.nature.com/articles/s41467-022-28109-x

The intrinsically disordered SARS-CoV-2 nucleoprotein in dynamic complex with its viral partner nsp3a	https://www.science.org/doi/10.1126/sciadv.abm4034
Rational design of highly potent, selective, and bioavailable SGK1 protein kinase inhibitors for the treatment of osteoarthritis	https://pubs.acs.org/doi/full/10.1021/acs.jmedchem.1c01601
Evolution and activation mechanism of the flavivirus class II membrane-fusion machinery.	https://www.nature.com/articles/s41467-022-31111-y
Altiratinib blocks Toxoplasma gondii and Plasmodium falciparum development by selectively targeting a spliceosome kinase	https://www.science.org/doi/10.1126/scitranslmed.abn3231
Discovery of BLU-945, a reversible, potent, and wild-type-sparing next-generation EGFR mutant inhibitor for treatment-resistant non-small-cell lung cancer	https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/acs.jmedchem.2c00704
From fragment to lead: De novo design and development toward a selective FGFR2 inhibitor	https://pubs.acs.org/doi/full/10.1021/acs.jmedchem.1c01163
Structure and function of a family of tick-derived complement inhibitors targeting properdin	https://www.nature.com/articles/s41467-021-27920-2
Substrate-inspired fragment merging and growing affords efficacious LasB inhibitors.	https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/full/10.1002/anie.202112295
Substrate recognition and cryo-EM structure of the ribosome-bound TAC toxin of Mycobacterium tuberculosis	https://www.nature.com/articles/s41467-022-30373-w
Structure of the decoy module of human glycoprotein 2 and uromodulin and its interaction with bacterial adhesin FimH	https://www.nature.com/articles/s41594-022-00729-3
Caspase-8 variant G regulates rheumatoid arthritis fibroblast-like synoviocyte aggressive behaviour.	https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/full/10.1002/acr2.11384
Structure-based and knowledge-informed design of B-Raf inhibitors devoid of deleterious PXR binding	https://pubs.acs.org/doi/full/10.1021/acs.jmedchem.1c01354
Molecular and in vivo studies of a glutamate-class prolyl-endopeptidase for coeliac disease therapy.	https://www.nature.com/articles/s41467-022-32215-1
Nanobodies protecting from lethal SARS-CoV-2 infection target receptor binding epitopes preserved in virus variants other than omicron	https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fimmu.2022.863831/full
Structural mechanism for tyrosine hydroxylase inhibition by dopamine and reactivation by Ser40 phosphorylation.	https://www.nature.com/articles/s41467-021-27657-y
Three-Dimensional Correlative Imaging of a Malaria-Infected Cell with a Hard X-ray Nanoprobe	https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/acs.analchem.8b05957

Synchrotron-based characterization of arthroprosthetic CoCrMo particles in human bone marrow	https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s10856-022-06675-2
Improving our understanding of metal implant failures: Multiscale chemical imaging of exogenous metals in ex-vivo biological tissues	https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/31173961/
Pulmonary exposure to metallic nanomaterials during pregnancy irreversibly impairs lung development of the offspring	https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/17435390.2017.1311381?journalCode=inan20
Evaluation of imaging setups for quantitative phase contrast nanoCT of mineralized biomaterials	https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1107/S1600577522003137
The Bronchial Circulation in COVID-19 Pneumonia	https://www.atsjournals.org/doi/abs/10.1164/rcm.202103-0594IM
A multiscale X-ray phase-contrast tomography dataset of a whole human left lung	https://www.nature.com/articles/s41597-022-01353-y
Imaging intact human organs with local resolution of cellular structures using hierarchical phase-contrast tomography	https://www.nature.com/articles/s41592-021-01317-x
EuXFEL	
X-ray screening identifies active site and allosteric inhibitors of SARS-CoV-2 main protease	https://www.science.org/doi/10.1126/science.abf7945
De novo determination of mosquitocidal Cry11Aa and Cry11Ba structures from naturally occurring nanocrystals	https://www.nature.com/articles/s41467-022-31746-x
Mechanisms of membrane protein crystallization in ‘bicelles’	https://www.nature.com/articles/s41598-022-13945-0
Megahertz pulse trains enable multi-hit serial femtosecond crystallography experiments at X ray free electron lasers	https://www.nature.com/articles/s41467-022-32434-6
Observation of substrate diffusion and ligand binding in enzyme crystals using high-repetition rate mix-and-inject serial crystallography	https://journals.iucr.org/m/issues/2021/06/00/mf5055/
3D diffractive imaging of nanoparticle ensembles using an x-ray laser	https://opg.optica.org/abstract.cfm?uri=optica-8-1-15
Time-resolved serial femtosecond crystallography at the European XFEL	https://www.nature.com/articles/s41592-019-0628-z
Megahertz single-particle imaging at the European XFEL	https://www.nature.com/articles/s42005-020-0362-y
Membrane protein megahertz crystallography at the European XFEL	https://www.nature.com/articles/s41467-019-12955-3
Femtosecond X-ray emission study of the spin cross-over dynamics in haem proteins	https://pubs.rsc.org/en/content/articlelanding/2021/fd/d0fd00131g

Ultrafast X-Ray Photochemistry at European XFEL: Capabilities of the Femtosecond X-Ray Experiments	https://www.mdpi.com/2076-3417/10/3/995
FELIX	
Metabolite Identification Using Infrared Ion Spectroscopy – Novel Biomarkers for Pyridoxine-Dependent Epilepsy	https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/acs.analchem.1c02896
Untargeted metabolomics and infrared ion spectroscopy identify biomarkers for pyridoxine-dependent epilepsy	https://www.jci.org/articles/view/148272
Amadori rearrangement products as potential biomarkers for inborn errors of amino-acid metabolism	https://www.nature.com/articles/s42003-021-01909-5
2-Methyl-pentanoyl-carnitine (2-MPC): a urine biomarker for patent <i>Ascaris lumbricoides</i> infection	https://www.nature.com/articles/s41598-020-72804-y
Mass spectrometry-based identification of ortho-, meta- and para-isomers using infrared ion spectroscopy	https://pubs.rsc.org/en/content/articlelanding/2020/an/d0an01119c
Reference-standard free metabolite identification using infrared ion spectroscopy	https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1387380619301587
Molecular identification in metabolomics using infrared ion spectroscopy	https://www.nature.com/articles/s41598-017-03387-4
Combined Liquid Chromatography-Infrared Ion Spectroscopy for Identification of Regioisomeric Drug Metabolites	https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/acs.analchem.7b00577
MAXIV	
Ultralarge Virtual Screening Identifies SARS-CoV-2 Main Protease Inhibitors with Broad-Spectrum Activity against Coronaviruses	https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/jacs.1c08402
Importance of Binding Site Hydration and Flexibility Revealed When Optimizing a Macrocyclic Inhibitor of the Keap1–Nrf2 Protein–Protein Interaction	https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/acs.jmedchem.1c01975
A FabG inhibitor targeting an allosteric binding site inhibits several orthologs from Gram-negative ESKAPE pathogens	https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0968089620307288
Crystal structures of NUDT15 variants enabled by a potent inhibitor reveal the structural basis for thiopurine sensitivity	https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/33753169/
An Experimental Toolbox for Structure-Based Hit Discovery for <i>P. aeruginosa</i> FabF, a Promising Target for Antibiotics	https://chemistry-europe.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/cmdc.202100302
Crystal Structures of Potent Dimeric Positive Allosteric Modulators at the Ligand-Binding Domain of the GluA2 Receptor	https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/acsmedchemlett.8b00369

SOLARIS	
Cryo-EM reconstructions of BMV-derived virus-like particles reveal assembly defects in the icosahedral lattice structure	https://pubs.rsc.org/en/content/articlelanding/2022/nr/d1nr05650f
Zn(II) binding causes interdomain changes in the structure and flexibility of the human prion protein	https://www.nature.com/articles/s41598-021-00495-0
Influence of interference effects on the spectral quality and histological classification by FT-IR imaging in transfection geometry	https://pubs.rsc.org/en/content/articlelanding/2021/an/d0an01565b
Translation of an esophagus histopathological FT-IR imaging model to a fast quantum cascade laser modality	https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/jbio.202000122
PrP (58–93) peptide from unstructured N-terminal domain of human prion protein forms amyloid-like fibrillar structures in the presence of Zn ²⁺ ions	https://pubs.rsc.org/en/content/articlelanding/2019/ra/c9ra01510h
Structures of substrate complexes of foamy viral protease-reverse transcriptase	https://journals.asm.org/doi/10.1128/JVI.00848-21
SOLEIL	
Virtual histology of an entire mouse brain from formalin fixation to paraffin embedding. Part 2: Volumetric strain fields and local contrast changes	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jneumeth.2021.109385
A High-Affinity Calmodulin-Binding Site in the CyaA Toxin Translocation Domain is Essential for Invasion of Eukaryotic Cells	https://doi.org/10.1002/adv.202003630
PB1-F2 amyloid-like fibers correlate with pro-inflammatory signaling and respiratory distress in influenza-infected mice	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbc.2021.100885
Catabolism of lysosome-related organelles in color-changing spiders supports intracellular turnover of pigments	https://www.pnas.org/doi/abs/10.1073/pnas.2103020118
Structural basis of cytokine-mediated activation of ALK family receptors	https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-021-03959-5
BRCA2 binding through a cryptic repeated motif to HSF2BP oligomers does not impact meiotic recombination	https://www.nature.com/articles/s41467-021-24871-6
Albumin-driven disassembly of lipidic nanoparticles: the	https://doi.org/10.1039/C9NR06485K

specific case of the squalene-adenosine nanodrug	
The Hantavirus Surface Glycoprotein Lattice and Its Fusion Control Mechanism	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cell.2020.08.023
Deciphering the Unexpected Binding Capacity of the Third PDZ Domain of Whirlin to Various Cochlear Hair Cell Partners	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmb.2020.09.012
A dual role in regulation and toxicity for the disordered N terminus of the toxin GraT	https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-019-08865-z
Structure of ATP citrate lyase and the origin of citrate synthase in the Krebs cycle	https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-019-1095-5

C) COLLABORATIVE PROJECTS

Title (Acronym)	Funder	Country (Funder)	Description	Link
ALBA-CELLS				
BIO2016-77883-C2-2-P (ConjuFunStruc)	MINECO (ES)-FEDER	ES	Preventing the spread of conjugative antibiotic resistance by studying the crucial proteins of the pLS20 conjugative plasmid at the structural level.	
MINICANCER	MINECO	ES	Spatial fractionation of the dose in charged particle radiotherapy: revealing the underlying biology with synchrotron light (MINICANCER).	
	AECC	ES	Revealing the secrets of heavy ion minibeam radiotherapy under the synchrotron light.	
H2020-INFRAIA-2018-2020 (iNEXT-Discovery)	H2020	EU		home Infrastructure for NMR, EM and X-rays for Translational Research (inext-discovery.eu)
H2020-ICT-2018-20 (CoCid)	H2020	EU		Home - Cocid
PID2020-117028GB-I00	MICIU	ES	Structural mechanisms of transcriptional regulation and exchange of genetic material in gram-positive bacteria and terrestrial plants.	
CHIMERA (starts end 2022)	MICIU	ES	Multifunctional Hybrid 2D Nanomaterials for their Therapy Application	
DESY				
HALOS - Interconnecting infrastructures for life	EU/ several partners	EU		HALOS HALOS (lu.se)

science research and innovation				
New avenues in information and data science: advanced imaging applications at the XFEL and cryo-EM frontier	Helmholtz-Russian Science Foundation	RUS/DE		-
Röntgen-Ångström-Cluster (RÅC)	Swedish-German governments	SE/DE		A German-Swedish research collaboration (rontgen-angstrom.eu)
Serial Femtosecond Crystallography (SFX) user consortium	Germany, United Kingdom, Sweden, Slovakia, Switzerland, United States and Australia	DE, UK, SE, RS, CH, US, AU		www.sfx-consortium.org
ELETTRA				
AntiHelix EU H2020-MSCA-ITN-2019 (15/01/2019)	H2020	EU	DNA helicases in genome maintenance: from molecular and cellular mechanisms to specific inhibitors as potential drugs	AntiHelix (elettra.eu)
BioMERA EU INFRASTRUCTURES/1216 (31/03/2017, 10/10/2018)	Eu, Republic of Cyprus	Eu, CY	Platform for Biosciences and Human Health in Cyprus: MicroCT Enabled and Synchrotron Radiation Enabled Analyses	Home - BIOMERA (cyi.ac.cy)
EXPLORA	National PNRA 2019		Founded but not active yet	-
ISIDORE EU H2020-INFRA-2021-EMERGENCY-02 (06/05/2021)	H2020	EU	A New Approach to Pandemic Preparedness & Responsiveness Research in Europe	ISIDORE project: services for infectious disease outbreak research (isidore-project.eu)
AIRC RECQ4	National AIRC Investigation GRANT IG 2017	IT		Elettra Sincrotrone Trieste
AIRC - SISSI	National	IT		-

				Provide a multidisciplinary, distributed and interconnected platform covering a wide range of biological targets, from molecules to tissues and organisms	INTEGRA - The first step to enhance CERIC's life science capabilities - Ceric (ceric-eric.eu)
INTEGRA	FOE CERIC Research Grant		EU		
GLIOMA FVG	Regional LR 13/2021		IT		-
EXSCALATE4CoV EU H2020-SC1-PHE-CORONAVIRUS-2020	H2020		EU	E4C aims at leveraging EU's supercomputing resources coupling them with some of the continent's best life-science research labs to counter international pandemics faster and more efficiently. EXSCALATE leverages a "chemical library" of 500 billion molecules, thanks to a processing capacity of more than 3 million molecules per second.	Home (exscalate4cov.eu)
EXOTHERA	InterReg ITALIA - AUSTRIA 2014-2020		IT, AT	Exosomes for regenerative, immunosuppressive, neuroprotective and oncosuppressive therapies	EXOTHERA / HomePage (elettra.eu)
TRANS-GLIOMA	InterReg Italia-Slovenia		IT, SL	New glioblastoma therapies via a translational cross-border research platform	TRANSGLIOMA Italia Slovenia (ita-slo.eu)
RENEWALS	FOE CERIC Research Grant		EU	RENEWALS project aims at overcoming the present limits in exploiting and understanding the "bio" phenomena at various levels by adding new capabilities to the characterization tools at CERIC-ERIC facilities for investigation of	Renewals - Graphene for Water in Life Sciences - Ceric (ceric-eric.eu)

			processes occurring in liquid environments.	
BIOMECC	Regional LR 17/2014	IT		
ESRF				
Towards the root cause of Alzheimer's	ANR	FR	The role of assembly factors mitochondrial complex I (MitoCompAs)	Au service de la science ANR
Fragment Screen EU INFRA-2022-TECH-01		EU		-
Centre for Doctoral Training (CDT) in Molecular Sciences for Medicine (MoSMed)	UK EPSRC	UK		About EPSRC – UKRI
iNEXT	H2020	EU		iNEXT meets Industry workshop (esrf.fr)
INNOVAXN	Horizon COFUND		InnovaXN is a doctoral training programme bringing together the expertise of large-scale research infrastructures with the R&D needs of European industry.	InnovaXN - Home page
High resolution Cryo-Electron Microscopy of Antibody - Antigen complexes	ANRT CIFRE	FR		CIFRE Association Nationale Recherche Technologie (anrt.asso.fr)
COSMETHICS-1 and 2	UGA??			Cosmetics - Accueil - Cosmetics (univ-grenoble-alpes.fr)
COVNSP3	ANR	FR	Nsp3 polyprotein of SARS-CoV2: structural studies and its exploration in drug screening campaign	https://anr.fr/
Anatomical to cellular synchrotron imaging of the whole human body	Chan Zuckerberg Initiative	US		Chan Zuckerberg Initiative - Building a Future for Everyone

Integration of functional and structural knowledge across scales to decipher information processing in the mammalian brain	UKRI and Wellcome Funding	UK		UKRI – UK Research and Innovation
Multi-scale Bio-imaging (precise title to be put)	Horizon Europe	EU		Horizon Europe European Commission (europa.eu)
EuXFEL				
SFX user Consortium	Wellcome trust MPI, UKRI, BMBF, ...			www.sfx-consortium.org
Candidates for COVID drugs	EXSCALATE4 CoV EU-H2020, Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG), Helmholtz Association, BMBF, Joachim-Herz-Stiftung Hamburg, DASHH (Data Science in Hamburg, ...			XFEL: Shining the light on candidates for COVID drugs
Studying coronavirus proteins using SAXS	EMBL and EuXFEL			Studying coronavirus proteins using small-angle X-ray scattering at European XFEL EMBL
Systematic studies for SFX of Membrane proteins (SSFxMP)	EuXFEL internal Research and Development			-

MS SPiDOC	EU FET OPEN	EU	The MS SPiDOC consortium combines internationally leading expertise in different fields relevant to the project: Instrument design and development, computer simulations as well as working with biomolecules in the gas phase and on SPI are combined to implement the novel sample environment at the next generation XFEL facility	MS SPiDOC – Mass Spectrometry for Single-Particle Imaging of Dipole Oriented Protein Complexes (ms-spdoc.eu)
FELIX				
BoostCrop	EU FET-OPEN	EU	Long term vision to develop a highly efficient, environmentally friendly and affordable foliar spray for crop growth enhancement and thus sustainable food security.	boostcrop.eu
Identification of drug metabolites using IRIS	TKI Chemistry (NL) + Janssen Pharma, Beerse (B)	NL, B		Analytical Ion Spectroscopy - FELIX Laboratory (ru.nl)
IRIS: a new dimension in mass spectrometry	NWO TTW	NL		Finished in 2022
MAXIV				
Fragment-screening by X-ray crystallography at MAX IV on an oncology-related protein from the Sprint Bioscience portfolio	VINNOVA	SE		Fragmentscreening för ett humant onkologirelaterat protein med hjälp av röntgenkristallografi vid MAX IV Vinnova
FragMAX	VR	SE	A facility for high throughput fragment screening in drug development by X-ray crystallography	Swecri - FragMAX - en plattform för high throughput screening av fragment i

				läkemedelsutveckling genom röntgenkristallografi (vr.se)
Nsp10-nsp14 komplex av SARS-CoV-2	Crafoord Foundation	SE		n/a
Röntgen-Ångström Cluster	RÅC	SE/DE		A German-Swedish research collaboration (rontgen-angstrom.eu)
HALOS - Interconnecting infrastructures for life science research and innovation	EU/ several partners	EU		HALOS HALOS (lu.se)
SOLARIS				
Three-dimensional orientation of macromolecules using infrared (IR) imaging and its importance in the cancer microenvironment	National Science Center	PL		
Enhancement of the histopathological classification based on FT-IR chemical imaging using data augmentation	National Science Center	PL		
Structural studies of proteins at high pressures on the BILBO line (former SOLCRYS line) at the SOLARIS National Synchrotron Radiation Center	National Science Center	PL		
Molecular basis of neurodegenerative diseases - the influence of selected metallic nanoparticles	National Science Center	PL		
SOLEIL				
REACTIV	anr	FR	Reassortment, Emergence and Factor of Virulence of Influenza A Virus	Reassortment, Emergence and Factor of Virulence of Influenza A Virus ANR

LiquidFact	anr	FR	Morphogenesis, organization and functions of liquid viral factories formed by Mononegavirales	Morphogenesis, organization and functions of liquid viral factories formed by Mononegavirales ANR
Time-resolved cryo-EM studies of translation initiation – TREMTI	anr	FR		Time-resolved cryo-EM studies of translation initiation ANR
CAFinDS	anr	FR	DNA-synthesis coupled histone assembly by the chaperone CAF-1	DNA-synthesis coupled histone assembly by the chaperone CAF-1 ANR
3DTransCyaA	anr	FR	Structures and translocation process of CyaA	Structures and translocation process of CyaA ANR
InXS	anr	FR	Integrative Xer recombination complex Stabilization	Integrative Xer recombination complex Stabilization ANR
Cob4SAM	anr	FR	Deciphering the mechanistic and structural diversity of B12-dependent radical SAM enzymes	Cob4SAM: Deciphering the mechanistic and structural diversity of B12-dependent radical SAM enzymes ANR
DeepSAXS	anr	FR	Deep contrast-variation SAXS: a new tool for structural biology	Deep contrast-variation SAXS: a new tool for structural biology ANR
iNext-Discovery	H2020	EU	Infrastructure for transnational access and discovery in structural biology	European Commission : CORDIS (europa.eu)

D) USER GROUPS

Facility	PI Name and Surname	User group	Country	Link
ALBA-CELLS				
ALBA-CELLS	Cecilia Jiménez	Sant Joan de Déu Research Institute	ES	Neuromuscular Diseases: research SJD Barcelona Children's Hospital (sjdhospitalbarcelona.org)
ALBA-CELLS	Pablo Gastaminza (Dep. Molecular and Cell Biology)	CNB	ES	https://www.cnb.csic.es/index.php/es/component/k2/item/296-pablo-gastaminza
ALBA-CELLS	Mark van Raaij (Struct Macrom)	CNB	ES	Structural biology of viral fibres (csic.es)
ALBA-CELLS	Juan Hermoso	IQFR-CSIC, Dep. Crystallography and Structural Biology	ES	Crystallography and Structural Biology. Cristallografia y Biología Estructural (CBE) (csic.es)
ALBA-CELLS	María Solà Vilarrubias	IBMB-CSIC, Dep. Structural and Molecular Biology	ES	Department of Structural and Molecular Biology IBMB (csic.es)
ALBA-CELLS	Adriana Rojas	CIC bioGUNE	ES	Groups CIC bioGUNE Center for Cooperative Research in Biosciences
ALBA-CELLS	Jose Gavira	Lab. for Crystallographic Studies	ES	Gavi's Site (csic.es)
ALBA-CELLS	Alberto Marina	IBV, Crystallography and Macrom. Unit	ES	Crystallography of Macromolecules Unit (csic.es)
ALBA-CELLS	Maria Elena Gonzalez Muñoz	University Malaga	ES	Dra. Elena González Muñoz – ComoTú (uma.es)
ALBA-CELLS	Marijana Petkovic	Vinca Institute Belgrade	RS	Marijana Petković, Naučni savetnik - Institut za nuklearne nauke "Vinča" (vinca.rs)
ALBA-CELLS	Immaculada Martínez-Rovira	UAB	ES	Imma Martínez-Rovira - Ramón y Cajal Researcher - Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona LinkedIn
ALBA-CELLS	Youlanda Prezado	Institute Curie	FR	YOLANDA PREZADO Institut Curie (institut-curie.org)
DESY				

DESY	Tim Salditt	Salditt	DE	Prof. Dr. Tim Salditt - Georg-August-Universität Göttingen (uni-goettingen.de)
DESY	Meytal Landau	DESY/EMBL/Technion	DE	Landau Group – Functional protein fibrils in microbial infections and aggregation diseases (embl.org)
			IL	Meytal Landau's Lab Functional Protein Fibrils in Microbial Infections and Aggregation Diseases (technion.ac.il)
DESY	Alke Meents & Henry Chapman	Meents & Chapman, DESY/CFEL	DE	Henry Chapman's Group (desy.de)
DESY	T.J. Lane	Lane, DESY/CFEL	DE	Photobiology (cfel.de)
DESY	Michael Kolbe	Kolbe, CSSB/HZI	DE	Structural Infection Biology (cssb-hamburg.de)
DESY	Wulf Blankenfeldt	Blankenfeldt, HZI	DE	Our Research Research Helmholtz Centre for Infection Research (helmholtz-hzi.de)
DESY	Charlotte Uetrecht	Utrecht, DESY/Siegen	DE	Dynamics of Viral Structures (cssb-hamburg.de)
DESY	Holger Sondermann	Sondermann,	DE	Molecular and Structural Microbiology (cssb-hamburg.de)
DESY	Poul Nissen	Nissen	DEN	Nissen Group (au.dk)
DESY	Lars Redecke & Rolf Hilgenfeld	Redecke & Hilgenfeld	DE	Redecke, Lars: BIOCHEMIE (uni-luebeck.de)
DESY	Christian Betzel	Betzel	DE	AG Betzel : Department of Chemistry : Universität Hamburg (uni-hamburg.de)
ELETTRA				
ELETTRA	Prof. Katarina Vogel-Mikuš	University of Ljubljana, Slovenia	SI	Staff - Information (ijs.si)
ELETTRA	Dr. Lorella Pascolo / Prof. Giuseppe Ricci	BURLO Hospital, Trieste, Italy	IT	Lorella Pascolo's lab IRCCS Ospedale Infantile Burlo Garofolo (Ospedale Burlo) (researchgate.net)
ELETTRA	Prof. Maria Grazia Ortore, Prof. Elisabetta Giorgini	Universita' Politecnica delle Marche, Italy	IT	Maria Grazia Ortore Università Politecnica delle Marche, Italy - Academia.edu
ELETTRA	Prof Stefan Salentinig	University of Fribourg, CH	CH	Salentinig Group Department of Chemistry University of Fribourg (unifr.ch)
ELETTRA	Prof. Giulio Caracciolo	University of Roma Sapienza, Italy	IT	Giulio Caracciolo Dipartimento di Chimica (uniroma1.it)
ELETTRA	Prof. Christian	Göttingen Univ Hosp. & Max	DE	Experimentelle Bildgebung – AG Dullin (umg.eu)

	Dullin, Frauke Alves	Plank (Göttingen, G)		
ELETTRA	Prof. Alessandro Olivo	UCL (London, UK)	UK	Professor Alessandro Olivo Medical Physics and Biomedical Engineering - UCL – University College London
ELETTRA	Prof. Alessandra Giuliani	Universita' delle Marche, Italy	IT	Alessandra Giuliani (0000-0003-4177-7441) (orcid.org)
ELETTRA	Prof. Mario Gimona & Eva Rohde	Spinal Cord Injury and Tissue Regeneration Center Salzburg, Austria	AT	SELECTBIO - Exosomes-EV-based Therapeutics Summit Speaker Biography (selectbiosciences.com)
ELETTRA	Dr. Valeria Rondelli & Prof. Paola Brocca	Università degli Studi di Milano, Italy	IT	Rondelli Valeria Maria Università degli Studi di Milano Statale (unimi.it)
ELETTRA	Dr. Ilaria Corsi	University of Siena, Italy	IT	Ilaria CORSI Professor (Associate) PhD Environmental Biology Università degli Studi di Siena, Siena UNISI Department of Environment, Earth and Physical Sciences (researchgate.net)
ELETTRA	Prof. Balasubrama nian Gopal	Indian Institute of Science Bangalore, India	IN	IISc (irins.org)
ELETTRA	Dr. Udipi A. Ramagopal	Poornaprajna Institute of Scientific Research, India	IN	Udipi A. Ramagopal – Poornaprajna Institute of Scientific Research Recognized by the Department of Scientific and Industrial Research (DSIR), Govt. of India and MAHE (ppisr.res.in)
EuXFEL				
EuXFEL	Alke Meents	FS-BMX (Biomedical Research with X-rays) - CFEL	DE	Dr. Alke Meents (cfel.de)
EuXFEL	Allen Orville	XFEL HUB Diamond light source UK	UK	Welcome to the XFEL Hub at Diamond - - Diamond Light Source
EuXFEL	Valentin Gordeliy	Membrane Transport Group (IBS Grenoble France)	DE	Valentin Gordeliy (fz-juelich.de)
EuXFEL	Connie Darmanin	Time resolved crystallography, La Trobe University	AU	Connie Darmanin Profile La Trobe University
EuXFEL	Marius Schmidt	Schmidt lab, University of	US	Schmidt Lab Schmidt Lab Website (uwm.edu)

		Wisconsin-Milwaukee		
EuXFEL	Edward Snell	Bio XFEL	US	BioXFEL - Home
EuXFEL	Henry Chapman	Coherent imaging team - CFEL	DE	Coherent Imaging Team (cfel.de)
EuXFEL	Thomas Schnider	EMBL	DE	EMBL Hamburg EMBL.org
FELIX				
FELIX	Ron Wevers and others	Translational Metabolic Laboratory, RadboudUMC	NL	Prof. Wevers, R.A. (Ron) Radboud University (ru.nl)
FELIX	Filip Cuyckens	Janssen Pharma	BE	Filip CUYCKENS Scientific Director & Fellow PhD Drug Metabolism & Pharmacokinetics (researchgate.net)
MAXIV				
MAXIV	Pål Stenmark	Stockholm University	SE	Pål Stenmarks forskargrupp - Stockholms universitet
MAXIV	Jette Kastrup	Copenhagen University	DEN	Jette Sandholm Jensen Kastrup - Staff (ku.dk)
MAXIV	Robert Schnell	Karolinska Institutet	SE	Robert Schnell Medarbetare (ki.se)
MAXIV	Ute Krengel	Oslo University	NOR	Ute Krengel - Department of Chemistry (uio.no)
SOLARIS				
SOLARIS	Sebastian Glatt	MCB UJ	PL	Sebastian Glatt – Glatt-lab
SOLARIS	Marcin Nowotny	Laboratory of Protein Structure - IIMCB	PL	Laboratories - IIMCB
SOLARIS	Maciej Kozak	Biomedical Physics Department, Adam Mickiewicz University Poznan	PL	Strona Zakładu Fizyki Makromolekularnej (amu.edu.pl)
SOLARIS	Joanna Depciuch	Institute of Nuclear Physics Polish Academy of Sciences	PL	Joanna DEPCIUCH PhD Department of Functional Nanomaterials (researchgate.net)

2. ENERGY

A) TOOLS / BEAMLINES

Beamline	Technique	Link
ALBA-CELLS		
BL01-MIRAS	Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy and microscopy	BEAMLINE INFORMATION — MIRAS (albasynchrotron.es)
BL04-MSPD	High angular resolution Powder Diffraction (XRD) Capabilities: Up to 8 coin cells cycling in parallel during the measurements.	BEAMLINE INFORMATION — MSPD (albasynchrotron.es)
BL09-MISTRAL	Full-field Transmission X-ray Microscopy for cryo nano-tomography in the water window for biological applications	BEAMLINE INFORMATION — MISTRAL (albasynchrotron.es)
BL11-NCD	Small and Wide Angle X-ray Scattering SAXS/WAXS (7-20 keV) Capabilities: 100ms acquisition time and space resolution from 1nm to 1 μ m.	BEAMLINE INFORMATION — NCD (albasynchrotron.es)
BL16-NOTOS	XAS (4.7-30 keV) and XRD (11-30 keV) Capabilities: Quasi-simultaneous access to XAS and XRD. Up to 8 coin cells cycling in parallel and minor constrains on the sample environment and around 1-5 min per spectrum.	BEAMLINE INFORMATION — NOTOS (albasynchrotron.es)
BL22-CLAESS	XAS (2.35-62.3 keV, S to Yb K-edges) and XES (6-22 keV) Capabilities in the full energy range (down to the S K-edge): Quasi-simultaneous access to XAS and XES. Up to 2 coin cells cycling in parallel and 1-5min per spectrum. Expandable FDA in-house developed software for fast online data post processing of big data set.	BEAMLINE INFORMATION — CLAESS (albasynchrotron.es)
BL24-CIRCE	Pressure X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy (NAPP-APXPS) and PhotoEmission Electron Microscope (PEEM) NAPP Capabilities: Simultaneous APXPS and cyclic voltammetry studies of solid electrolyte batteries, XAS and XPS operando studies of liquid electrolyte batteries. PEEM Capabilities: Imaging and spectroscopic information of the nucleation, growth and anode formation with 30 nm of space	BEAMLINE INFORMATION — CIRCE (albasynchrotron.es)

	resolution and time resolution down to the femto-second range.	
DESY		
P01	High-resolution dynamics (IXS, RIXS)	Beamline P01 - High Resolution Dynamics Beamline (desy.de)
P02.1	Powder diffraction & total scattering (XRD)	Beamline P02.1 - Powder Diffraction and Total Scattering Beamline (desy.de)
P03	X-ray scattering MINAXS (SAXS/WAXS)	Beamline P03 - The Micro- and Nanofocus X-ray Scattering Beamline (desy.de)
P04	XUV (ARPES)	Beamline P04 - Variable Polarization XUV Beamline (desy.de)
P06	Scanning X-ray microscopy (XRF, XBIC, XEOL, XRD, ptychography)	Beamline P06 - Hard X-ray Micro/Nano-Probe (desy.de)
P07	High-energy tomography (Hereon) & high-energy XRD (DESY) with focused beam	Beamline P07 - The High Energy Materials Science Beamline
P08	High-resolution XRD	n.a.
P21	High-energy XRD with large beam	Beamline P21 - Swedish Materials Science Beamline (desy.de)
P22	HAXPES	Beamline P22 - Hard X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy (desy.de)
P23	In-situ XRD	n.a.
P62	SAXS/WAXS	Beamline P62 - SAXSMAT (desy.de)
P64	XAFS	Beamline P64 - Advanced X-ray Absorption Spectroscopy (desy.de)
P65	XAFS	Beamline P65 - Applied X-ray Absorption Spectroscopy (desy.de)
Diamond Light Source		
B18	Core EXAFS	Beamline B18 - Diamond Light Source
I11	High Resolution Powder Diffraction	Beamline I11 - Diamond Light Source
I09	Surface and Interface Structural Analysis	Beamline I09 - Diamond Light Source
I15-1	X-ray Pair Distribution Function	Beamline XPDF (I15-1) - Diamond Light Source
I12	Joint Engineering, Environmental & Processing (JEEP)	Beamline I12 – JEEP - Diamond Light Source
I13-2	Diamond Manchester Imaging	Beamline I13-2 - Diamond Light Source

ePSIC	Aberration corrected electron microscopy	electron Physical Science Imaging Centre (ePSIC) - - Diamond Light Source
I21	Resonant Inelastic X-ray Scattering	Beamline I21 - Diamond Light Source
I13-1	Coherence	Beamline I13-1 - Diamond Light Source
I14	Hard X-ray Nanoprobe	Beamline I14 - Diamond Light Source
I15	X-ray powder diffraction experiments at extreme conditions (pressures and temperatures)	Beamline I15 - Diamond Light Source
B07	C-Versatile Soft X-ray beamline: Ambient Pressuer XPS & NEXAFS	Beamline B07 - Diamond Light Source
I18	Microfocus Spectroscopy	Beamline I18 - The Microfocus Beamline - Diamond Light Source
I07	Surface and Interface Diffraction	Beamline I07 - Diamond Light Source
I08	Diamond Scanning X-ray Microscopy	Beamline I08 - Diamond Light Source
I10	Advanced Dichroism Experiments	Beamline I10 - Diamond Light Source
I19	Small Molecule Single Crystal Diffraction	Beamline I19 - Diamond Light Source
I20	X-ray Absorption Spectroscopy (XAS) on challenging samples, X-ray Emission Spectroscopy (XES), Energy Dispersive EXAFS (EDE)	Beamline I20 - Diamond Light Source
B22	Multimode InfraRed Imaging And Microspectroscopy (MIRIAM)	Beamline B22 - Diamond Light Source
ELETTRA		
ALOISA	PES, XAFS in TEY and Time-resolved PES in pump-probe mode using laser	Elettra Sincrotrone Trieste ALOISA
APE	ARPES, PES, XAFS, in-operando and ambient pressure spectroscopy	Elettra Sincrotrone Trieste APE
BACH	PES, XAFS in TEY and TFY, XES and cells for studies in liquid environment	Elettra Sincrotrone Trieste BACH
BEAR	XAFS-EXAFS, PES, soft XES, X-ray excited luminescence (XEOL)	Elettra Sincrotrone Trieste BEAR
ESCAMicroscopy	Scanning Photoelectron microscope (SPEM) including NAP cell	Elettra Sincrotrone Trieste ESCA Microscopy
Materials Science	PES and XAFS in TEY	Elettra Sincrotrone Trieste Materials Science
MCX	Non-single crystal XRD, including grazing angle and reflectivity	Elettra Sincrotrone Trieste MCX
Nanospectroscopy- NanoESCA	XPEEM, SPELEEM and CDI in reflective geometry	Elettra Sincrotrone Trieste NanoESCA
SAXS	SAXS-WAXS, GISAXS and pump-probe ps X-ray scattering	Elettra Sincrotrone Trieste SAXS
SuperESCA	High resolution PES and XAFS in TEY	Elettra Sincrotrone Trieste SuperESCA
TwinMic	Multifunctional - STXM, XRM, XAS, ptychography & XRF imaging	Elettra Sincrotrone Trieste TwinMic

XAFS	Hard X-ray XAFS-EXAFS in TFY and transmission	Elettra Sincrotrone Trieste XAFS
EuXFEL		
SPB/SFX	Serial femtosecond crystallography, single particle imaging, MHz microscopy	Scientific Instrument SPB/SFX (xfel.eu)
FXE	Pump-probe XES, WAXS, XRD (resonant and non-resonant), powder diffraction, limited versions of XAS/XANES/RXES and SAXS	Scientific Instrument FXE (xfel.eu)
SXP (2023)	femtosecond time-resolved photoelectron spectroscopy	n.a.
FELIX 1&2		
FELIX 1&2	IR action spectroscopy of dilute samples of molecules IR sum-frequency generation (SFG) spectroscopy IR-IR and IR-NIR pump-probe spectroscopy	User stations - FELIX Laboratory (ru.nl)
FELICE	IR action spectroscopy of dilute samples of molecules	User stations - FELIX Laboratory (ru.nl)
HZB		
BEIChem-PGM	BEIChem station: NEXAFS, EXAFS, XPS, mass spectrometry, time-resolved absorption SpAnTeX: NEXAFS, XPS, NAP-XPS, HAXPES	BEIChem-PGM - Helmholtz-Zentrum Berlin (HZB) (helmholtz-berlin.de)
CPMU17 and UE48	-CAT (catalytic reactions under ambient pressure conditions) -MYSTIIC (Microscope for X-ray Scanning Transmission In-situ Imaging of Catalysts) -OAESE (Operando Absorption and Emission Spectroscopy) -PINK (X-ray emission spectroscopy) -SISSY I (XPS, HAXPES, XAS, XES, XRF)	CPMU17 EMIL - Helmholtz-Zentrum Berlin (HZB) (helmholtz-berlin.de)
ENERGIZE	EXAFS, NEXAFS, XPS, UPS, ARPES	ENERGIZE - Helmholtz-Zentrum Berlin (HZB) (helmholtz-berlin.de)
SISS	XPS, NAP-XPS, XAS, NEXAFS, mass spectrometry, time-resolved absorption	SISS station - Helmholtz-Zentrum Berlin (HZB) (helmholtz-berlin.de)
KMC-1	HAXPES, EXAFS, NEXAFS, XANES	KMC-1 - Helmholtz-Zentrum Berlin (HZB) (helmholtz-berlin.de)
KMC-2	XRD, XANES, EXAFS, XRF, XRR	KMC-2 - Helmholtz-Zentrum Berlin (HZB) (helmholtz-berlin.de)
KMC-3 CryoEXAFS	EXAFS, XAS, XANES, XRF	CryoEXAFS - Helmholtz-Zentrum Berlin (HZB) (helmholtz-berlin.de)
PM4 LowDosePE S	NEXAFS, XPD, XPS, UPS, ARPES, time-resolved PES and absorption	PM4 - Helmholtz-Zentrum Berlin (HZB) (helmholtz-berlin.de)

U41-PEAXIS	NEXAFS, EXAFS, XPS, ARPES, RIXS	U41-PEAXIS - Helmholtz-Zentrum Berlin (HZB) (helmholtz-berlin.de)
UE49-PGM SMART	Spectro-Microscopy with aberration correction for relevant techniques	UE49 PGM SMART - Helmholtz-Zentrum Berlin (HZB) (helmholtz-berlin.de)
UE52-SGM SOL ³ PES	NEXAFS, XPS, UPS, NAP-XPS, ARPES	SOL³PES - Helmholtz-Zentrum Berlin (HZB) (helmholtz-berlin.de)
MAXIV		
NanoMAX	Hard X-ray nanoprobe	NanoMAX – MAX IV (lu.se)
DanMAX	Materials science	DanMAX – MAX IV (lu.se)
Balder	X-ray absorption spectroscopy (XAS) and X-ray emission spectroscopy (XES) in medium and hard X-ray energy range	Balder – MAX IV (lu.se)
ForMAX	Combining full-field tomographic imaging, small- and wide-angle x-ray scattering (SWAXS), and scanning SWAXS imaging	ForMAX – MAX IV (lu.se)
CoSAXS	Multipurpose Small Angle X-ray Scattering (SAXS)	CoSAXS – MAX IV (lu.se)
BioMAX	X-ray macromolecular crystallography	BioMAX – MAX IV (lu.se)
MicroMAX	Parallel and intense X-ray beam, X-ray crystallography	MicroMAX – MAX IV (lu.se)
Veritas	RIXS (Resonant Inelastic X-ray Scattering)	Veritas – MAX IV (lu.se)
HIPPIE	Ambient pressure X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (APXPS)	HIPPIE – MAX IV (lu.se)
SoftiMAX	Soft X-ray beamline, dedicated to spectromicroscopy and coherent imaging	SoftiMAX – MAX IV (lu.se)
FemtoMAX	Femtosecond X-ray beamline	FemtoMAX – MAX IV (lu.se)
MAXPEEM	Spectroscopic PhotoElectron and Low Energy Electron Microscope (SPELEEM)	MAXPEEM – MAX IV (lu.se)
SPECIES	Undulator based soft X-ray: Ambient Pressure X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy (APXPS), X-ray Absorption Spectroscopy (XAS), X-ray Emission Spectroscopy (XES) and Resonant Inelastic X-ray Scattering (RIXS)	SPECIES – MAX IV (lu.se)
FlexPES	Flexible PhotoElectron Spectroscopy	FlexPES – MAX IV (lu.se)
PSI		
SIM	Surfaces / Interfaces Microscopy; Soft-X-ray absorption spectroscopy (XAS), X-ray photoemission electron microscopy (XPEEM)	SIM - Paul Scherrer Institut (PSI)
Phoenix	Tender-X-ray microspectroscopy, Tender X-ray absorption spectroscopy (XAS)	Phoenix - Paul Scherrer Institut (PSI)

Super-XAS	X-ray absorption and emission spectroscopy (XAS and XES); Hard-X-ray absorption spectroscopy (XAS)	SuperXAS - Paul Scherrer Institut (PSI)
TOMCAT	Tomographic Microscopy and Coherent Radiology Experiments X-ray tomography	TOMCAT - Paul Scherrer Institut (PSI)
ADRESS	Advanced Resonant Spectroscopies (RIXS)	ADRESS - Paul Scherrer Institut (PSI)
Micro-XAS	Micro X-ray Absorption Spectroscopy (micro-XRD), (micro-XRF), (micro-XANES)	Micro XAS - Paul Scherrer Institut (PSI)
MS-Powder	Materials Science Beamline - Powder Diffraction (XRD)	MS - Paul Scherrer Institut (PSI)
SOLARIS		
PIRX	X-ray absorption spectroscopy (XAS), (including bioXAS)	PIRX - SOLARIS National Synchrotron Radiation Centre (uj.edu.pl)
ASTRA	X-ray absorption in tender and hard X-ray energy range	ASTRA - SOLARIS National Synchrotron Radiation Centre (uj.edu.pl)
URANOS (former UARPES)	Angle-resolved X-ray photoemission spectroscopy (VUV range)	URANOS - SOLARIS National Synchrotron Radiation Centre (uj.edu.pl)
PHELIX	Angle-resolved X-ray photoemission spectroscopy (Soft X-ray range)	PHELIX - SOLARIS National Synchrotron Radiation Centre (uj.edu.pl)
DEMETER	Photoemission electron microscope (PEEM) Scanning transmission X-ray microscope (STXM)	DEMETER - SOLARIS National Synchrotron Radiation Centre (uj.edu.pl)
POLYX	Microscopy and tomography with hard X-rays	POLYX - SOLARIS National Synchrotron Radiation Centre (uj.edu.pl)
SOLEIL		
ROCK	Quick EXAFS	ROCK - SOLEIL French national synchrotron facility (synchrotron-soleil.fr)
GALAXIES	XES / XAS, RIXS, HAXPES	GALAXIES - SOLEIL French national synchrotron facility (synchrotron-soleil.fr)
ANATOMIX	Nanotomography, Coherent Imaging	ANATOMIX - SOLEIL French national synchrotron facility (synchrotron-soleil.fr)
SIXS	Surface Interface X-ray Scattering	SIXS - SOLEIL French national synchrotron facility (synchrotron-soleil.fr)
HERMES	STXM	HERMES - SOLEIL French national synchrotron facility (synchrotron-soleil.fr)
SWING	SAXS, WAXS	SWING - SOLEIL French national synchrotron facility (synchrotron-soleil.fr)
CRISTAL	XRD	CRISTAL - SOLEIL French national synchrotron facility (synchrotron-soleil.fr)
AILES	IR spectroscopy	AILES - SOLEIL French national synchrotron facility (synchrotron-soleil.fr)
TEMPO	XPS / NAP-XPS	TEMPO - SOLEIL French national synchrotron facility (synchrotron-soleil.fr)
PSICHE	XRD ; Tomography	PSICHÉ - SOLEIL French national synchrotron facility (synchrotron-soleil.fr)

B) PUBLICATIONS

Publication	Link
ALBA-CELLS	
Role of Manganese in Lithium- and Manganese-Rich Layered Oxides Cathodes	https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/acs.jpcclett.9b01174
Spatial Distributions of Discharged Products of Lithium-Oxygen Batteries Revealed by Synchrotron X-ray Transmission Microscopy	https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/acs.nanolett.5b02862
Revising the role of chromium on the surface of perovskite electrodes: Poison or promoter for the solid oxide electrolysis cell performance?	https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0021951719305883?via%3Dihub
Chemistry and Electrocatalytic Activity of Nanostructured Nickel Electrodes for Water Electrolysis	https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/acscatal.0c00856
On the catalytic and degradative role of oxygen-containing groups on carbon electrode in non-aqueous ORR	https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0008622320311854
Interface Sensitivity in Electron/Ion Yield X-ray Absorption Spectroscopy: The TiO ₂ -H ₂ O Interface	https://pubs.acs.org/doi/abs/10.1021/acs.jpcclett.1c02115
Understanding the nature of the passivation layer enabling reversible calcium plating	https://pubs.rsc.org/en/content/articlelanding/2020/EE/D0EE02347G
Laser Fabrication of Hybrid Electrodes Composed of Nanocarbons Mixed with Cerium and Manganese Oxides for Supercapacitive Energy Storage	https://pubs.rsc.org/en/content/articlelanding/2021/TA/D0TA06756C
Controlled poling of a fully printed piezoelectric PVDF-TrFE device as a multifunctional platform with inkjet-printed silver electrodes	https://pubs.rsc.org/en/content/articlelanding/2022/TC/D2TC01913B
Quantification of charge compensation in lithium- and manganese-rich Li-ion cathode materials by x-ray spectroscopies	https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2542529322000852?via%3Dihub
Role of Manganese in Lithium- and Manganese-Rich Layered Oxides Cathodes	https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/acs.jpcclett.9b01174
Local Interactions Governing the Performances of Lithium- and Manganese-Rich Cathodes	https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/acs.jpcclett.0c03462
Continuous Carbon Channels Enable Full Na-Ion Accessibility for Superior Room-Temperature Na-S Batteries	https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/adma.202108363
Lithium/Oxygen Incorporation and Microstructural Evolution during Synthesis of Li-Rich Layered Li[Li _{0.2} Ni _{0.2} Mn _{0.6}]O ₂ Oxides	https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/aenm.201803094
Effects of nanostructuring on the bond strength and disorder in V ₂ O ₅ cathode material for rechargeable ion-batteries	https://pubs.rsc.org/en/content/articlelanding/2018/cp/c8cp00716k
VIV Disproportionation Upon Sodium Extraction From Na ₃ V ₂ (PO ₄) ₂ F ₃ Observed by Operando X-ray Absorption Spectroscopy and Solid-State NMR	https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/acs.jpcc.6b11413

Lithium/Oxygen Incorporation and Microstructural Evolution during Synthesis of Li-Rich Layered Li[Li 0.2 Ni 0.2 Mn 0.6]O 2 Oxides	https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/aenm.201803094
BESSY II	
ACS Applied Energy Materials (2022): Unveiling the Energy Alignment across Ultrathin 4P-NPD Hole Extraction Interlayers in Organic Solar Cells	https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/acsaem.2c00350
Nano Energy 101 (2022): Ceria nanoparticles as promoters of CO ₂ electroreduction on Ni/YSZ: An efficient preparation strategy and insights into the catalytic promotion mechanism	https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S2211285522006413
ACS Applied Materials & Interfaces (2022), Separating the Effects of Band Bending and Covalency in Hybrid Perovskite Oxide Electrocatalyst Bilayers for Water Electrolysis	https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/acsaem.1c20337
Nature Communications (2022): A-site cation influence on the conduction band of lead bromide perovskites,	https://www.nature.com/articles/s41467-022-31416-y
Advanced Energy Materials (2022): Nanostructured Intermetallic Nickel Silicide (Pre)Catalyst for Anodic Oxygen Evolution Reaction and Selective Dehydrogenation of Primary Amines	https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/full/10.1002/aenm.202200269
ACS Catalysis (2022): Dynamics at Polarized Carbon Dioxide/Iron Oxyhydroxide Interfaces Unveil the Origin of Multicarbon Product Formation	https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/acscatal.1c04296
ACS Catalysis (2022): Electrocatalytic Conversion of Glycerol to Oxalate on Ni Oxide Nanoparticles-Modified Oxidized Multiwalled Carbon Nanotubes	https://pubs.acs.org/doi/abs/10.1021/acscatal.1c04150
Advanced Energy Materials (2022): Determining Structure-Activity Relationships in Oxide Derived Cu-Sn Catalysts During CO ₂ Electroreduction Using X-Ray Spectroscopy	https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/aenm.202103328
Small 18 (2022): Facilitating Reversible Cation Migration and Suppressing O ₂ Escape for High Performance Li-Rich Oxide Cathodes	https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/sml.202201014
Current Opinion in Electrochemistry (2022): Merging operando and computational X-ray spectroscopies to study the oxygen evolution reaction	https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2451910322001041
Angewandte Chemie, international Edition (2021) Fluoride Chemistry in Tin Halide Perovskites	https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/anie.202107599
Advanced Materials, Review Article: "The Pivotal Role of s-, d-, and f-Block Metals in Water Electrolysis: Status Quo and Perspectives"	https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/adma.202108432
Advanced Energy Materials (2021) Requirements for beneficial electrochemical restructuring: A model study on a cobalt oxide in selected electrolytes	https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/aenm.202101737
Advanced Functional Materials (2020) Simultaneous X-Ray Diffraction and Tomography Operando Investigation of Aluminum/Graphite Batteries	https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/adfm.202003913

Materials Today (2018): Advancing knowledge of electrochemically generated lithium microstructure and performance decay of lithium ion battery by synchrotron X-ray tomography	https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1369702118311131
Materials Horizon (2018): Crystalline silicon solar cells with tetracene interlayers: the path to silicon-singlet fission heterojunction devices	https://pubs.rsc.org/en/content/articlelanding/2018/mh/c8mh00853a
Diamond Light Source	
B18-Core EXAFS	
I11-High Resolution Powder Diffraction	-
I09-Surface and Interface Structural Analysis	-
I15-1-X-ray Pair Distribution Function (XPDF)	-
I12-JEEP: Joint Engineering, Environmental & Processing	-
I13-2-Diamond Manchester Imaging	-
ePSIC (EM)	-
I21-Resonant Inelastic X-ray Scattering (RIXS)	-
I13-1-Coherence	-
I14-Hard X-ray Nanoprobe	-
I15-Extreme Conditions	-
B07-C-Versatile Soft X-ray beamline: Ambient Pressure XPS & NEXAFS	-
I18-Microfocus Spectroscopy	-
I07, I08, I10, I19, I20, B22	-
ELETTRA	
Beyond the Oxygen Redox Strategy in Designing Cathode Material for Batteries: Dynamics of a Prussian Blue-like Cathode Revealed by Operando X-ray Diffraction and -ray Absorption Fine Structure and by a Theoretical Approach (Marco Giorgetti et al)	https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/acs.jpcc.8b12116
Pushing Stoichiometries of Li-Rich Layered Oxides Beyond Their Limits (Sergio Brutti et al)	https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/acsaem.1c03396
In situ photoelectron spectromicroscopy for the investigation of solid oxide-based electrochemical systems (Benedetto Bozzini et al)	https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/B9780128182857000034
Development of vanadium-based polyanion positive electrode active materials for high voltage sodium-based batteries (Seguei Fedotov et al)	https://www.nature.com/articles/s41467-022-31768-5
Spectroscopic Insights into the Electrochemical Mechanism of Rechargeable Calcium/Sulfur Batteries (Robert Dominko, Iztok Arvon, Lorenzo Stievano et al)	https://pubs.acs.org/doi/abs/10.1021/acs.chemmater.0c02074
Cobalt oxide-supported Pt electrocatalysts: intimate correlation between particle size, electronic metal-support interaction and stability (Jörg Libuda et al)	https://pubs.acs.org/doi/abs/10.1021/acs.jpcclett.0c02233

On the catalytic and degradative role of oxygen-containing groups on carbon electrode in non-aqueous ORR (Lada Yashina, Danil Itkins et al)	https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0008622320311854
Effect of the synthesis method on the properties of lithium doped graphene oxide composites with tin oxide nanoparticles (Ana Cremades et al)	https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0022369718331627
EuXFEL	
Unsupervised learning approaches to characterizing heterogeneous samples using X-ray single-particle imaging	https://asu.pure.elsevier.com/en/publications/unsupervised-learning-approaches-to-characterizing-heterogeneous-
FELIX	
Zooming in on the initial stages of catalytic NO reduction using metal clusters	https://pubs.rsc.org/en/content/articlelanding/2022/cp/d1cp05760j
Water Splitting by a C60-Supported Single Vanadium Atom	https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/anie.202112398
Carbide Dihydrides: Carbonaceous Species Identified in Ta ⁴⁺ Mediated Methane Dehydrogenation	https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/anie.202010794
Selective C-H Bond Cleavage in Methane by Small Gold Clusters	https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/anie.201706009
Ultrafast phononic switching of magnetization	https://www.nature.com/articles/s41567-020-01124-9
Ultrafast nonthermal photo-magnetic recording in a transparent medium	https://www.nature.com/articles/nature20807
MAX IV	
Atomic-Scale Tuning of Graphene/Cubic SiC Schottky Junction for Stable Low-Bias Photoelectrochemical Solar-to-Fuel Conversion	https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/acsnano.0c00986
In Situ Imaging of Ferroelastic Domain Dynamics in CsPbBr ₃ Perovskite Nanowires by Nanofocused Scanning X-ray Diffraction	https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/acsnano.0c07426
Probing a battery electrolyte drop with ambient pressure photoelectron spectroscopy, Julia Maibach, Ida Källquist, Margit Andersson, Samuli Urpelainen, Kristina Edström, Håkan Rensmo, Hans Siegbahn & Maria Hahlin	https://www.nature.com/articles/s41467-019-10803-y
Potentials in Li-Ion Batteries Probed by Operando Ambient Pressure Photoelectron Spectroscopy.	https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/acsnano.1c12465
Divins, N.J., Kordus, D., Timoshenko, J. et al. Operando high-pressure investigation of size-controlled CuZn catalysts for the methanol synthesis reaction.	https://www.nature.com/articles/s41467-021-21604-7
Robert H. Temperton ¹ , Jack Hart, Nektarios Verykokkos, Elizabeth Gibson, James N. O'Shea A soft x-ray probe of a titania photoelectrode sensitized with a triphenylamine dye	https://aip.scitation.org/doi/abs/10.1063/5.0050531

Electrochemical and structural characterization of lithiation in spray deposited ordered mesoporous titania as an anode for Li ion batteries	https://pubs.rsc.org/en/content/articlelanding/2020/ra/d0ra02687e
20.8% Slot-Die Coated MAPbI ₃ Perovskite Solar Cells by Optimal DMSO-Content and Age of 2-ME Based Precursor Inks	https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/aenm.202003460
PSI	
Investigation of Li-ion solvation in carbonate based electrolytes using near ambient pressure photoemission	https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s11244-015-0518-2
Solving the puzzle of Li ₄ Ti ₅ O ₁₂ surface reactivity in aprotic electrolytes in Li-ion batteries by nanoscale XPEEM spectromicroscopy	https://pubs.rsc.org/en/content/articlelanding/2018/ta/c7ta09673a
Revealing the dual surface reactions on a HE-NCM Li-ion battery cathode and their impact on the surface chemistry of the counter electrode	https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/acsami.8b19511
Post mortem and operando XPEEM: a surface-sensitive tool for studying single particles in Li-Ion battery composite electrodes	https://dx.doi.org/10.1021/acs.analchem.9b04124
Study of graphite cycling in sulfide solid electrolytes	https://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1149/1945-7111/aba36f
Instability of PVDF binder in the LiFePO ₄ versus Li ₄ Ti ₅ O ₁₂ Li-Ion battery cell	https://doi.org/10.1002/hlca.202000183
Unveiling the complex redox reactions of SnO ₂ in Li-ion batteries using operando X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy and in situ X-ray absorption spectroscopy	https://doi.org/10.1021/acsami.0c17936
Performance-limiting factors of graphite in sulfide-based all-solid-state lithium-ion batteries	https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0013468621010252
High performance doped Li-rich Li _{1+x} Mn _{2-x} O ₄ cathodes nanoparticles synthesized by facile, fast, and efficient microwave assisted hydrothermal route	https://pubs.acs.org/doi/abs/10.1021/acsam.2c00902
Evidence for stepwise formation of solid electrolyte interphase in a Li-ion battery	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enism.2021.10.013
Operando Visualization of Morphological Dynamics in All-Solid-State Batteries	https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/aenm.201901547
In situ X-ray diffraction characterisation of Fe _{0.5} TiOPO ₄ and Cu _{0.5} TiOPO ₄ as electrode material for sodium-ion batteries	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.electacta.2015.06.105
Influence of Conversion Material Morphology on Electrochemistry Studied with Operando X-Ray Tomography and Diffraction	https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/adma.201403792
Combined operando X-ray diffraction–electrochemical impedance spectroscopy detecting solid solution reactions of LiFePO ₄ in batteries	https://www.nature.com/articles/ncomms9169
Correlated X-Ray 3D Ptychography and Diffraction Microscopy Visualize Links between Morphology and Crystal Structure of Lithium-Rich Cathode Materials	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.isci.2018.12.028

Direct evidence of an unanticipated crystalline phase responsible for the high performance of few-layered-MoS ₂ anodes for Na-ion batteries	https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S2405829722001696
Influence of Na/Mn arrangements and P2/P'2 phase ratio on the electrochemical performance of Na _x MnO ₂ cathodes for sodium-ion batteries	https://doi.org/10.1039/C9TA12176E
The impact of oxygen evolution and cation migration on the cycling stability of a Li-rich Li[Li _{0.2} Mn _{0.6} Ni _{0.1} Co _{0.1}]O ₂ positive electrode	https://doi.org/10.1039/D0TA05556E
Phosphorus anionic redox activity revealed by operando P K-edge X-ray absorption spectroscopy on diphosphonate-based conversion materials in Li-ion batteries	https://pubs.rsc.org/en/content/articlehtml/2018/cc/c8cc01350k
Operando characterization of intermediates produced in a lithium-sulfur battery	https://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1149/2.0081507jes
Redox dynamics of sulphur with Ni/GDC anode during SOFC operation at mid- and low-range temperatures: An operando S K-edge XANES Study	https://www.researchgate.net/publication/257226039_Redox_dynamics_of_sulphur_with_NiGDC_anode_during_SOFC_operation_at_mid_and_low-range_temperatures_An_operando_S_K-edge_XANES_study
Visualization of dissolution-precipitation processes in lithium-sulfur batteries	https://doi.org/10.1002/aenm.202103126
Gas diffusion layers with deterministic structure for high performance polymer electrolyte fuel cells	https://pubs.acs.org/doi/abs/10.1021/acsaami.0c20896
Laser structured gas diffusion layers for improved water transport and fuel cell performance	https://pubs.acs.org/doi/abs/10.1021/acsaami.1c02454
Unraveling two-phase transport in porous transport layer materials for polymer electrolyte water electrolysis	https://pubs.rsc.org/en/content/articlelanding/2021/ta/d1ta03379d
Operando liquid pressure determination in polymer electrolyte fuel cells	https://pubs.acs.org/doi/abs/10.1021/acsaami.1c04560
Visualizing plating-induced cracking in lithium-anode solid-electrolyte cells	https://doi.org/10.1038/s41563-021-00967-8
Investigation of the transient freeze start behavior of polymer electrolyte fuel cells	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2020.229447
Understanding the effect of feed gas humidity on the freeze start behavior of polymer electrolyte fuel cells	https://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1149/1945-7111/ac37ed
Effects of gas diffusion layer substrates on PEFC water management: Part I. Operando liquid water saturation and gas diffusion properties	https://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1149/1945-7111/ac1035/meta
Temperature dependent water transport mechanism in gas diffusion layers revealed by subsecond operando X-ray tomographic microscopy	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2021.229492
Droplet and percolation network interactions in a fuel cell gas diffusion layer	https://doi.org/10.1149/1945-7111/ab8c85
Hierarchically structured porous transport layers for polymer electrolyte water electrolysis	https://doi.org/10.1002/aenm.201903216

Monitoring the morphological changes of Si-based electrodes by X-ray computed tomography: a 4D-multiscale approach	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nanoen.2020.104848
Optimal image denoising for in situ X-ray tomographic microscopy of liquid water in gas diffusion layers of polymer electrolyte fuel cells	https://doi.org/10.1149/1945-7111/ab9820
Improving water management in fuel cells through microporous layer modifications: fast operando tomographic imaging of liquid water	https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Improving-water-management-in-fuel-cells-through-of-Nagai-Eller/e407727c8632f2f598a266bc9b75fb8bf2ce7649
Exploring sub-second and sub-micron X-ray tomographic imaging of liquid water in PEFC gas diffusion layers	https://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1149/09208.0011ecst
In-situ observation of water evaporation in exhaust gas catalyst via sub-micron and sub-second X-ray tomography	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cesx.2021.100091
Washcoating of catalytic particulate filters studied by time-resolved X-ray tomography	https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1385894720341747?via%3Dihub
Drying of water from porous structures investigated by time-resolved X-ray tomography	https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/07373937.2022.2076239
Hyperpolarised xenon MRI and time-resolved X-ray computed tomography studies of structure-transport relationships in hierarchical porous media	https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1385894720328783?via%3Dihub
SOLARIS	
Abnormal Phenomena of Multi-Way Sodium Storage in Selenide Electrode	https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/adfm.202102406
Origin of extra capacity in advanced Li-Rich cathode materials for rechargeable Li-Ion batteries	https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1385894721018805
The Effect of Cobalt Incorporation into Nickel-Iron Oxide/(oxy)hydroxide Catalyst on Electrocatalytic Performance Toward Oxygen Evolution Reaction	https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/ente.202100688
Synthesis Attempt and Structural Studies of Novel A(2)CeWO(6) Double Perovskites (A(2+) = Ba, Ca) in and outside of Ambient Conditions	https://pubs.acs.org/doi/abs/10.1021/acsomega.2c00669
Evaluation of applicability of Nd- and Sm-substituted Y1-xRxMnO3+delta in temperature swing absorption for energy-related technologies	https://ideas.repec.org/a/eee/energy/v239y2022ipes0360544221026785.html
SOLEIL	
Understanding Battery Interfaces by Combined Characterization and Simulation Approaches: Challenges and Perspectives. Duncan Atkins et al.	https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/aenm.202102687
Accelerating battery characterization using neutron & synchrotron techniques: towards a multi-modal and multi-scale standardized experimental workflow. Duncan Atkins et al.	https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/aenm.202102694

C) COLLABORATIVE PROJECTS

Title (Acronym)	Funder	Link
ALBA-CELLS		
NovaCO2	MICIU (ES)	
ALBA-ICMAB (Barcelona, ES) collaboration in the framework of the CSIC PTI+ (Alta Tecnología Clave para la Transición en el Ciclo Energético)	Next Generat	https://pti-transener.csic.es/banco-alba/
New materials and methods to realise the high energy density 3b/4a battery (MAT4BAT)	AEI (ES)	
Post-doc fellowship focused on the battery investigation	RECONEGU T	
ReMade-at-ARI (101058414)	HE	
H2020-MSCA-COFOUND-2016. Doctoral training programme in Functional Advanced Materials	H2020	
BESSY II		
BEIChem - Berlin Joint Lab for	National	https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/08940886.2022.2082209

Electrochemical Interfaces		
CatLab - Catalysis Laboratory	National	http://hz-b.de/catlab
Care-O-Sene - Catalyst Research for Sustainable Kerosene	National	https://care-o-sene.com/en/
Kopernikus – Power2X	National	www.kopernikus-projekte.de/en/projects/p2x
operaXX – operando investigations of cathode materials	National	www.aqua-cluster.de/de/projekte/operaxx/
CLINT – Catalysis at liquid interfaces	National	https://gepris.dfg.de/gepris/projekt/431791331?language=en
SITA - Stable Inorganic Tandem solar cells with superior device efficiency and increased durability	EU	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101075626
Diamond Light Source		
Spectroscopy: Energy Materials BAG in B18 led by Alan Chadwick (Kent) and Giannantonio Cibin, Research Grant Making XAS surface sensitive: Development of new capabilities at B18 funded by STFCbatteries.org, Giannantonio Cibin is a partner on NEXGENNA		
Spectroscopy – Block Allocation Group: Beamtime: total of 3 days/semester, 3 visits x 1 days beamtime Total individual proposals run: 177 from Feb 2015 up to December 2021		

Crystallography Group: Phil Chater (I15-1 principal beamline scientist) was a CI on the original ReLiB grant and continues collaborations with partners on that grant and more widely
 Maria Diaz-Lopez (I15-1 beamline scientist) has a research focus in batteries, especially operando cell development and studies including interfaces
 Rachel Tang is a 4th Year Diamond/Birmingham PhD student associated with beamline I15-1 co-supervised by Phil Chater and Phoebe Allan
 Chris Foo is a 4th Year Diamond/Oxford PhD student associated with beamline I11 co-supervised by Sarah Day and Edman Tsang
 A PhD studentship with UCL for a 2022 start associated with beamline I15 has been awarded to Christine Beavers and Dean Keeble to work with Alex Rettie and Rhodri Jervis
 Supporting researchers from the DEGRADATION, ReLiB, FUTURECAT, CATMAT, SOLBAT I11 Cambridge BAG for new materials characterisation and structure-property relationships for a zero-carbon future (Claire Grey)
 I15-1 Oxford Warwick Midlands Solid State Chemistry BAG to study local structure-property relationships in solids (Andrew Goodwin)

Imaging Group: Imaging experiments from various Faraday projects via – Paul Shearing UCL group
 Dorota Matras - PDRA funded through CATMAT
 PDRA's jointly funded through Faraday Characterisation project (project completed)
 Jointly funded PDRA with Johnson Matthey – electrochemical cell for correlative electron microscopy and X-ray studies
 Jointly funded PDRA with Stranks group – Perovskite solar cells

ELETTRA

KNOWSKITE-X: Electrode materials chemical -to-power devices	HORIZON-CL4-2022-RESILIENCE-01-(CRNS, F - 8 partners)	Under preparation- just approved
DOC-FAM: Training in Functional Advanced Materials	HORIZON-MSCA-2021-COFUND-01 (10/02/2022) (CSIC– S - 5 partners, incl. also ALBA)	https://docfam.icmab.es/
DESTINY: Doctorate Program on Materials for Energy Storage	H2020-MSCA-COFUND-2019 (26/09/2019) (CRNS- F – 40 partners, incl also SOLEIL)	https://www.destiny-phd.eu/

SMART-X: Charge transfer dynamics	H2020-MSCA-ITN-2019 (15/01/2019) (CNR-I-11 partners, incl. also DESY)	https://www.smartx-itn.eu/
FIDELITY: Decoupling Electron and Ion Transport in battery	HORIZON-CL5-2022-D2-01 (06/09/2022) (Uni Bologna – I)	Waiting final evaluation
MEGS: MultiExciton Generation in Synthesized molecular heterojunctions	PRIN 2022 (31/03/2022) (CNR-IOM)	
e-DyNaFOx: Electron Dynamics in Nanostructured Functional Oxides	PRIN 2022 (31/03/2022) (Uni – Bologna, Modena, Calabria)	
OPFELIA: Operando studies of active materials for Na-Ion battery cathodes	PRIN 2022 (31/03/2022) (Uni – Bologna, CNR)	
EuXFEL		
UltraBat (submitted September 2022)	EU batteries	
ChameLi-ion (submitted September 2022)	EU batteries	
FELIX		
Materials for Sustainability: CO2 to formate	NWO	

CATCHY: CATalytic CO2 HYdrogenatio n	EU / MCSA European training network	www.catchy-etn.eu
National Roadmap Program for Large Scale Facilities	NL	
Shaken and switched: tracking the dynamics of phono magnetic recording	NWO	
MAXIV		
Imaging nanoparticle surface catalysis with coherent X- rays	Crafoord Foundation	
A new Soft X- ray Spectroscopy Branchline as an Experimental Platform for Battery and Metal Industries in Sweden	Swedish Research Council	
in-FORM. In- situ platform for formation of energy materials	Swedish Foundation for Strategic Research	
PSI		
Sub-second dynamics of liquid water transport in polymer electrolyte fuel cells revealed by 4D X-ray	SNSF	https://data.snf.ch/grants/grant/166064

Tomographic Microscopy		
Collaboration with Toyota on fuel cell research		
SOLARIS		
Number of users' projects founded by National Science Centre		
SOLEIL		
RS2E – French Network for Energy storage	CNRS, MESRF	https://www.energie-rs2e.com/
IFPEN – Institut Français du Pétrole / Energie Nouvelle	Private / Public	https://www.ifpenergiesnouvelles.fr/
BIG MAP - Battery Interface Genome - Materials Acceleration Platform	H2020	https://www.big-map.eu/big-map
Destiny – Doctorate programme on Emerging battery Storage Technologies INspiring Young Scientist	H2020	https://www.destiny-phd.eu/

D) USER GROUPS

PI Name and Surname	User group/ Area	City	Country	Link
ALBA-CELLS				
Rosa Palacin, Dino Tonti, Alexander Ponrouch, Angel Perez	ICMAB-CSIC	Barcelona	ES	ICMAB - Solid State Chemistry
Stefano Passerini	Electrochemistry for Batteries, Helmholtz Institute	Ulm	DE	Prof. Dr. Stefano Passerini - European Training Network POLYSTORAGE (polystorage-etn.eu)
Dominic Bresser	Electrochemical Energy Storage Materials, Helmholtz Institute	Ulm	DE	Electrochemical Energy Storage Materials – Helmholtz-Institut Ulm (hiu-batteries.de)
Claudia D. Simao	Eurecat, Catalonia Tech Center	Barcelona	ES	Claudia Simão Eurecat - Academia.edu
Shehab Ali	Suez Canal University	Ismailia	EG	Shehab ALI Lecturer Ph.D. Suez Canal University, Ismailia Department of Physics (researchgate.net)
Wojciech Olszewski	University of Bialystok	Bialystok	PL	Wojciech Olszewski – Wydział Fizyki, Uniwersytet w Białymstoku (uwb.edu.pl)
Naurang Saini	University of Rome	Rome	IT	NAURANG L. SAINI MATHEMATICAL MODELS FOR ENGINEERING, ELECTROMAGNETICS AND NANOSCIENCES (uniroma1.it)
Montserrat Casas, Marcus Fehse, Gene Noils	CICEnergyGUNE	Álava	ES	Basque Research & Technology Alliance CIC energiGUNE
Lorenzo Stievano, Christian Masquelier, Laurence Croguennec	Energie RS2E	Amiens Cedex	FR	Home RS2E (energie-rs2e.com)
Robert Weatherup	University of Oxford	Oxford	UK	Home Energy Materials Interfaces (ox.ac.uk)
Antonio de Lucas Consuegra	Universidad de Castilla La Mancha	Ciudad Real	ES	Antonio LUCAS-CONSUEGRA Lecturer University of Castilla-La Mancha, Ciudad Real Department of Chemical Engineering profile on ResearchGate

Víctor A. de la Peña O'Shea	Imdea Energía	Madrid	ES	https://www.energia.imdea.org/personal/investigadores/dr-victor-de-pena
DESY				
Andreas Stierle / Thomas Keller	Nanolab (DESY)	Hamburg	DE	X-ray Physics and Nanoscience (DESY NanoLab)
Michael Stuckelberger	FS-PETRA (DESY)	Hamburg	DE	Michael STUCKELBERGER Researcher PhD Deutsches Elektronen-Synchrotron, Hamburg DESY Group PETRA III (researchgate.net)
Simone Techert	FS-SCS (DESY)	Hamburg	DE	Simone Techert - Deutsches Elektronen-Synchrotron DESY
Stephan Roth	FS-PE (DESY) / KTH	Hamburg	DE	Prof. Dr. Stephan V. Roth (desy.de)
Patrick Huber	TUHH	Hamburg	DE	Prof. Dr. Patrick Huber : Department of Chemistry : Universität Hamburg (uni-hamburg.de)
Thomas Sheppard	KIT	Karlsruhe	DE	KIT - IKFT - Institute - Staff - Thomas Sheppard
Diamond Light Source				
Prof A. Chadwick, Dr E. McCabe, Dr M. Alfredsson, Dr S. Ramos	University of Kent	Kent	UK	Alan Chadwick - Materials for Energy and Electronics - Research at Kent
Prof S. Skinner, Prof M. Ryan	Imperial College London	London	UK	Home - Professor Stephen Skinner (imperial.ac.uk)
Prof M. Rosseinsky, Dr L. Hardwick	University of Liverpool	Liverpool	UK	Rosseinsky Group - Department of Chemistry - University of Liverpool
Prof P. Bruce, Dr E. Boivin	University of Oxford	Oxford	UK	The Bruce Group The Bruce Group (ox.ac.uk)
Prof J. Irvine, Dr R. Armstrong	University of St Andrews	St Andrews	UK	John Irvine – JTSI Group – Energy and Materials in St Andrews (st-andrews.ac.uk)
Prof C. Grey	University of Cambridge	Cambridge	UK	Professor Dame Clare Grey FRS Yusuf Hamied Department of Chemistry (cam.ac.uk)
Prof I. Parkin, Prof G. Sankar, Dr J. Darr	University College London	London	UK	Ivan Parkin Chemistry - UCL – University College London
Prof A. Russell, Prof J. Owen, Prof A. Hector	University of Southampton	Southampton	UK	Professor Andrea Russell University of Southampton

Prof S. Cussen	University of Sheffield	Sheffield	UK	Group – Cussen group Energy Materials Research at Sheffield (cussengroupsheffield.com)
Prof D. Gregory	Univarsity of Glasgow	Glasgow	UK	The Gregory Research Group - Inorganic Solid State and Materials Chemistry [University of Glasgow]
Dr N. Tapia-Ruiz	Lancaster University	Lancaster	UK	The Tapia-Ruiz Group - Group (tapiaruizgroup.com)
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Prof. Sergio Brutti	Università degli studi di Roma La Sapienza	Rome	IT	Sergio Brutti Dipartimento di Chimica (uniroma1.it)
EuXFEL				
Professor Jiawei Mi	Hull University	Hull	UK	Professor Jiawei Mi University of Hull
Kartik Ayer	MPI for structure and dynamics	Hamburg	DE	Ayyer Group @ MPSD (kartikayyer.com)
FELIX				

Joost Bakker	Cluster mediated reactions (CO ₂ , CH ₄ activation & utilization, NO reduction)	NIJMEGEN	NL	dr. J.M. (Joost) Bakker - HFML - FELIX (ru.nl)
Andrei Kirilyuk	Ultrafast magneto-optics	NIJMEGEN	NL	prof. dr. A. (Andrei) Kirilyuk - HFML - FELIX (ru.nl)
HZB				
Beatriz Roldan Cuenya, Robert Schlögl	Fritz-Haber-Institut	Berlin	DE	Fritz Haber Institute Fritz Haber Institute of the Max Planck Society (mpg.de)
Serena DeBeer, Robert Schlögl	MPI für Chemische Energiekonversion	Muelheim a.d.R.	DE	Prof. Dr. Serena DeBeer MPI CEC (mpg.de)
Erik Nibbering	Max-Born-Institut	Berlin	DE	Erik T. J. Nibbering Max-Born-Institut (mbi-berlin.de)
Olga Kasian, Marcus Bär	Helmholtz-Institut Erlangen-Nürnberg für erneuerbare Energien	Erlangen	DE	HI ERN DE (hi-ern.de)
Holger Dau, Elena Voloshina	Freie Universität Berlin	Berlin	DE	Freie Universität Berlin: Startseite (fu-berlin.de)
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Elena Savinova	Uni Strasbourg ICPEES	Strasbourg	FR	Elena Savinova - ICPEES - Université de Strasbourg (unistra.fr)
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Eva Kovacevic	GREMI – Université d'Orléans	Orléans	FR	Eva Kovacevic Université d'Orléans (univ-orleans.fr)
Yuriy Dedkov	Ensemble3 Centre of Excellence	Warsaw	PL	ENSEMBLE 3 - Centre of Excellence
Håkan Rensmo	Uppsala Universitet	Uppsala	SE	Håkan Rensmo - Uppsala universitet (uu.se)
MAXIV				
M. Hahlin	Li-ion batteries	Uppsala	SE	Maria HAHLIN Assistant Professor Uppsala University, Uppsala UU Department of Physics and

				Astronomy (researchgate.net)
H. Rensmo	Novel photovoltaic materials	Uppsala	SE	Håkan Rensmo - Uppsala University, Sweden (uu.se)
James O'Shea	Dye-sensitized solar cells	Nottingham	UK	James O'Shea (nottingham.ac.uk)
E. L. Unger	Synthesis of metal-halide perovskites for photovoltaic applications.	Berlin	DE	Eva UNGER Research Group Leader PhD Helmholtz-Zentrum Berlin, Berlin HZB (researchgate.net)
Olena Zavorotynska	Synthesis of Zr-based MOFs	Stavanger	NOR	Ansattprofil #721 Universitetet i Stavanger (uis.no)
Prof. Dr. Simone Mascotto	Formation of metal alloy nanoparticles from parent perovskite oxide	Hamburg	DE	Prof. Dr. Simone Mascotto : Department of Chemistry : Universität Hamburg (uni-hamburg.de)
Beatriz Roldan Cuenya, Robert Schlögl	Fe and Cu based catalysts for CO2 hydrogenation	Berlin	DE	Fritz Haber Institute Fritz Haber Institute of the Max Planck Society (mpg.de)
Bo Brummerstedt Iversen	Hydrothermal synthesis of nanomaterials	Aarhus	DEN	The Interdisciplinary Nanoscience Center at Aarhus University: Bo Brummerstedt Iversen (au.dk)
B. Ranvsbæk	Li-ion batteries	Aarhus	DEN	https://ravnsbaekgroup.com
P. Norby	Li-ion batteries	Kongens Lyngby	DEN	P. NORBY Technical University of Denmark, Kongens Lyngby DTU Department of Energy Conversion and Storage (researchgate.net)
Jianwu Sun	Artificial photosynthesis	Linköping	SE	Jianwu Sun - Linköping University (liu.se)
Jesper Wallentin	Perovskite nanowires	Lund	SE	Jesper Wallentin, Associate Prof. Division of Synchrotron Radiation Research (lu.se)
William Brant	Li-ion batteries	Uppsala	SE	William Brant - Uppsala University, Sweden (uu.se)
Anders E. C. Palmqvist	Li-ion batteries	Gothenburg	SE	Anders Palmqvist Chalmers
Hilde Johnsen Venvik	Hydrogen purification membranes	Trondheim	NOR	Hilde Johnsen Venvik - NTNU
Jeppe Vang Lauritsen	Cu-Zn catalysts for CO2 reduction	Aarhus	DEN	Jeppe Vang Lauritsen - Research - Aarhus University

Nina Lock	Elucidating MOF catalyst structure during electrocatalytic CO ₂ reduction	Aarhus	DEN	Nina Lock - Research - Aarhus University (au.dk)
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SOLARIS				
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SOLEIL				
Several research groups	IEMN	Lille	FR	Les groupes de recherche – IEMN
Dr. Matthieu Becuwe	LRCS	Amiens	FR	Organic, hybrid and polymeric materials for energy (u-picardie.fr)
Antonella Iadecola	CSE	Paris	FR	Solid-State Chemistry and Energy Lab – Research towards better energy storage and conversion systems (solid-state-chemistry-energy-lab.org)
Armelle Ringuedé	IRCP	Paris	FR	Chemistry Research Institute of Paris (IRCP) - Chimie ParisTech - PSL
Laurent Michot	PHENIX	Paris	FR	Physicochimie des Électrolytes et Nanosystèmes interfaciaux - Michot Laurent (cnrs.fr)
	LCMCP	Paris	FR	LCMCP (upmc.fr)
	IS2M	Mulhouse	FR	About us - IS2M (uha.fr)
	CHRISMAT	Caen	FR	- CRISMAT (cnrs.fr)

	LAMBE	Evry	FR	LAMBE - Laboratoire Analyse, Modélisation, Matériaux pour la Biologie et l'Environnement (univ-evry.fr)
	IMN	Nantes	FR	The Institute (cnrs-imn.fr)
	CEMHTI	Orléans	FR	Home CEMHTI CNRS UPR3079 Orléans France (cnrs-orleans.fr)
	LEPMI	Grenoble	FR	LEPMI presentation - LEPMI (grenoble-inp.fr)
Dany Carlier-Larregaray	ICMCB	Bordeaux	FR	Energy : Materials and Batteries - ICMCB - Institut de Chimie de la Matière Condensée de Bordeaux (cnrs.fr)
	CIRIMAT	Toulouse	FR	CIRIMAT (cnrs.fr)
	ICG	Montpellier	FR	ICGM-UMR5253 - www.icgm.fr
Ryszard Lobinski	IPREM	Pau	FR	Chairs - Institute of analytical and physicochemical sciences for the environment and materials (IPREM) - University of Pau and Pays de l'Adour (UPPA) (univ-pau.fr)
	ICR	Marseille	FR	Homepage - Institut de Chimie Radicale (univ-amu.fr)

ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Description
ACE2-RBD	angiotensin-converting enzyme 2 - receptor-binding domain
AECC	Association Against Cancer
AFM	Atomic force microscopy
AIRC	Associazione italiana per la Ricerca sul Cancro
ALK	Anaplastic lymphoma kinase
ANR	Agence nationale de la recherche
ANRT	Association Nationale recherche technologie
APXPS	Ambient-Pressure X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy
ARPES	Angle resolved photoelectron spectroscopy
Acy	ATP citrate lyase
BMV	brome mosaic virus
BRCA2	BReast CANcer gene 2
CAT	Catalytic reactions under ambient pressure conditions
CBN	Centro Nacional de Biotecnologia
CDI	Coherent Diffraction Imaging
CDT	Centre for Doctoral Training
CEMHTI	Conditions Extrêmes et Matériaux: Haute Température et Irradiation, Orléans
CERIC	Central European Research Infrastructure Consortium
CFEL	Center for Free-Electron Laser Science
CHRISMAT	Laboratoire de Cristallographie et Sciences des Matériaux
CIC bioGUNE	Center for Cooperative Research in Biosciences
CIFRE	Conventions Industrielles de Formation par la Recherche
CIRIMAT	Centre Interuniversitaire de Recherche et d'Ingénierie des Matériaux
CNRS	The French National Centre for Scientific Research
CoCrMo	cobalt-chromium-molybdenum
CoV	coefficient of variation
cryo-EM	cryogenic electron microscopy
CSE	Solid-State Chemistry and Energy Lab, Paris
CSIC	Spanish National Research Council
CSIC	Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas
DMSO	Dimethyl sulfoxide
DNA	Deoxyribonucleic acid
EDE	Energy Dispersive EXAFS
EGFR	Estimated Glomerular Filtration Rate
EM	Electron Microscopy
EMBL	European Molecular Biology Laboratory
ePSIC	electron Physical Science Imaging Centre
EPSRC	Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council
ERK-RSK	extracellular signal-regulated kinase - ribosomal S6 kinase
ESKAPE	Enterococcus faecium, Staphylococcus aureus, Klebsiella pneumoniae, Acinetobacter baumannii, Pseudomonas aeruginosa, and Enterobacter species
ETH Zurich	Swiss Federal Institute of Technology
EXAFS	Extended X-ray absorption fine-structure

EXSCALATE	EXaScale smArt pLatform Against paThogEns
FEG	Field Emission Gun
FET	Future Emerging Technologies
FGFR2	Fibroblast Growth Factor Receptor 2
FTICR	Fourier-transform ion cyclotron resonance
FTIR	Fourier Transform Infrared
GISAXS	Grazing-incidence Small Angle X-ray Scattering
GREMI	Groupe de Recherches sur l'Energétique des Milieux Ionisés
H2020	Horizon 2020
HALOS	Hanseatic League of Science
HAXPES	Hard X-ray Photo-Electron Spectroscopy
HE-NCM	high manganese high energy - nickel cobalt manganese
IBMB	Molecular Biology Institute of Barcelona
IBV	Instituto Biomedicina de Valencia
ICG	Institut Charles Gerhardt
ICMAB	Institut de Ciència de Materials de Barcelona
ICMCB	Institut de Chimie de la Matière Condensée de Bordeaux
ICPEES	Institute of Chemistry and Processes for Energy, Environment and Health, Strasbourg
ICR	Institut de Chimie Radicalaire
IEMN	Institute of Electronics, Microelectronics and Nanotechnology
IIMCB	International Institute of Molecular and Cell Biology in Warsaw
IMN	Institut des Matériaux Jean Rouxel, Nantes
INSA Lyon	Institute national des Sciences Appliquées
IPREM	The Institute of Analytical Sciences and Physico-Chemistry for Environment and Materials
IQFR	Instituto de Química Física Rocasolano, Madrid
IR	Infrared laser
IRCP	Chemistry Research Institute of Paris
IRIS	Infrared ion spectroscopy
IS2M	Institut de Science des Matériaux de Mulhouse
ISIDORE	INTEGRATED SERVICES FOR INFECTIOUS DISEASE OUTBREAK RESEARCH
IXS	Inelastic X-ray scattering
JAK	Janus kinase
JEEP	Joint Engineering, Environmental & Processing
KIT	Karlsruhe Institute of Technology
LAMBE	Laboratoire Analyse, Modélisation, Matériaux pour la Biologie et l'Environnement
LCMCP	Le laboratoire de Chimie de la Matière Condensée de Paris
LEPMI	Le Laboratoire d'Electrochimie et de Physicochimie des Matériaux et des Interfaces, Grenoble
LpqH	19 kDa Mycobacterium tuberculosis lipoprotein
LRCS	Laboratoire de Réactivité et Chimie des Solides
LSD1	Lysine-specific histone demethylase 1A
MCX	Material Characterization by X-ray Diffraction

MICIU	Ministry of Science, Innovation and Universities
MINAXS	Micro- and Nano- focus X-ray Scattering
MINECO	Ministerio de Economía Y Competitividad
MIRIAM	Multimode InfraRed Imaging And Microspectroscopy
MPC	Methyl-pentanoyl-carnitine
mRNA	messenger ribonucleic acid
MS	Mass spectrometer
MS SPiDOC	Mass Spectrometry for Single-Particle Imaging of Dipole Oriented Protein Complexes
MX	Macromolecular Crystallography
MYSTIC	Microscope for X-ray Scanning Transmission In-situ Imaging of Catalysts
NAD(+)	nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide
NAD(H)	nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide + hydrogen
NAP	Near-ambient pressure
NAPP	near ambient pressure photoemission
NAP-XPS	Near-ambient pressure X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy
NDRG1	N-myc downstream regulated gene
NEXAFS	Near Edge X-ray Absorption Fine Structure
NOW	Dutch Research Council
NP	Cerium dioxide nanoparticles
NUDT15	Nudix Hydrolase 15
OAESE	Operando Absorption and Emission Spectroscopy
O-PTIR	optical Photothermal Infrared spectroscopy
ORR	objective response rate
PEEM	PhotoEmission Electron Microscope
PEFC	polymer electrolyte fuel cells
PES	Photo-Electron Spectroscopy
PHENIX	Physicochimie des Électrolytes et Nanosystèmes interfaciaux
PPVF	L'Institut Photovoltaïque d'Île-de-France
PSI	Paul Scherrer Institute
PVDF-TrFE	Polyvinylidene fluoride or polyvinylidene difluoride - trifluoroethylene
PXR	pregnane X receptor
RÅC	Röntgen-Ångström-Cluster
RBD	receptor-binding domain
RIXS	Resonant inelastic X-ray scattering
RXES	Resonant soft X-ray emission spectroscopy
SARS	Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome
SAXS	Small Angle X-ray Scattering
SFX	Serial Femtosecond Crystallography
SOFC	Solid Oxide Fuel Cell
SPELEEM	Spectroscopic photoemission and low energy electron microscope
SPeM	Scanning Photoelectron microscope
SPOR	Sporulation-related repeat
SSFxMP	Systematic studies for SFX of Membrane proteins
s-SNOM	Scattering Scanning Nearfield Optical Microscopy
STXM	Scanning transmission X-ray microscopy

SXP	Soft X-ray Port
TEY	Total Electron Yield
TFY	Total fluorescence Yield
TTW	Applied and Technical Sciences
TUHH	The Hamburg University of Technology
TXRF	Total reflection X-ray fluorescence
UCL	University College London
UGA	Université Grenoble Alpes
UKRI	UK Research and Innovation
UPS	UV Photoelectron Spectroscopy
VR	The Swedish Research Council
VUV	vacuum ultraviolet radiation
WAXS	Wide Angle X-ray Scattering
XAFS	X-ray absorption fine-structure
XANES	X-ray Absorption Near Edge Structure
XAS	X-ray absorption spectroscopy
XBIC	X-ray beam induced current
XEOL	X-ray excited optical luminescence
XES	X-ray emission spectroscopy
XFEL	X-ray free-electron laser facility
XPD	X-ray Powder Diffraction
XPDF	X-ray Pair Distribution Function
XPEEM	X-ray Photoemitted Electron Microscopy
XPS	X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy
XRD	X-ray diffraction
XRF	X-ray Fluorescence
XRM	X-ray microscopy
XRR	X-ray Reflectivity
XUV	Extreme ultraviolet